

Manuscript Details

Manuscript number	ATE_2020_177_R1
Title	Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study
Article type	Original Research Papers

Abstract

The dual production of power and freshwater by the combination of Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants and desalination units, technology known as CSP+D, may help to solve the energy and water scarcity problems in arid and semi-arid regions. The lack of accurate annual analyses, crucial for the proper selection of the best CSP+D configuration, hampers the investment in this technology that has not been implemented on an industrial scale so far. This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an annual assessment of power and freshwater production of CSP+D plants, based on a very accurate solar field model that uses time steps of 10 seconds. Three CSP+D configurations have been analyzed in two different locations, Abu Dhabi (UAE) and Almería (Spain). Two of the three CSP+D configurations consider the multi-effect distillation (MED) technology for freshwater production, in low-temperature and thermocompression modes. The latter also accounts for the water and electricity demands for the selection of the best coupling arrangement. The annual results of the CSP+MED systems have been finally compared with those obtained from the third configuration, a Reverse Osmosis (RO) unit connected to a CSP plant. Results obtained indicate that, in both locations, the configuration leading to maximum water and electricity productions is CSP+RO (26% more of freshwater in Almería and 10% more in Abu Dhabi). Only if the specific energy consumption of the RO process is above 5.4-5.6 kWh/m³, the most optimum configuration would be CSP+MED at low temperature.

Keywords	Simulation tool; Annual operation; CSP+D; Multi-effect distillation; Reverse Osmosis
Taxonomy	Energy Production, Energy Sustainability Assessment, Thermal Engineering, Solar Energy, Renewable Energy System, Simulation Tool for Optimization
Corresponding Author	Patricia Palenzuela
Corresponding Author's Institution	CIEMAT
Order of Authors	Patricia Palenzuela, Bartolomé Ortega Delgado, Diego Alarcón-Padilla
Suggested reviewers	Carlos Mata-Torres, Massimo Moser

Submission Files Included in this PDF

File Name [File Type]

Cover letter_Patricia Palenzuela 2020.pdf [Cover Letter]

Responses to Reviewer #1_FINAL.docx [Response to Reviewers]

Responses to Reviewer #2_FINAL.docx [Response to Reviewers]

Responses to Reviewer #3_FINAL.docx [Response to Reviewers]

Responses to Reviewer #4_FINAL.docx [Response to Reviewers]

Editor_FINAL.docx [Response to Reviewers]

Manuscript_Palenzuela et al 2020_changes highlighted.docx [Revised Manuscript with Changes Marked]

Highlights_Palenzuela et al 2020.docx [Highlights]

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Research Data Related to this Submission

Data set

<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/hfvdj52pyk/draft?a=e08e483d-1613-4820-a233-52ce105736b2>

Data for: Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an annual assessment of power and freshwater production of CSP+D plants, basing on a very accurate solar field model that takes meteorological data with time steps lower than 10 seconds. Three CSP+D configurations have been analyzed in two different locations, Abu Dhabi (UAE) and Almería (Spain). Two of the three CSP+D configurations consider the multi-effect distillation (MED) technology for freshwater production, in low-temperature and thermocompression modes. The latter also accounts for the water and electricity demands for the selection of the best coupling arrangement. The annual results of the CSP+MED systems have been finally compared with respect to those obtained from the third configuration, a Reverse Osmosis (RO) unit connected to a CSP plant.

Almería 27 March 2020

Editor
Applied Thermal Engineering

Dear Editor,

Attached you can find the article whose name is “Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study” wrote by Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado, Dr. Diego C. Alarcón-Padilla.

This work presents a simulation tool that allows the assessment of the annual electricity and freshwater production of CSP+D plants basing on a very accurate solar field model that takes meteorological data with time steps lower than 10 seconds. The simulation tool has been built by the integration of customizable quasi-static models and accounts for the water and electricity demands for the selection of the best coupling arrangement of the CSP+D plant. This tool can be very useful for performing reliable economic models sue to the accuracy of the CSP model in contrast with most of models found in the literature that use hourly steps.

The manuscript has been modified according to all the suggestions made by the reviewers. All the changes have been highlighted in yellow. We forgot to put the track changes on when we did the modifications but the changes can be distinguished clearly since they are highlighted in yellow.

Please, reconsider the paper for its publication in Applied Thermal Engineering.

Yours, sincerely

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Corrections for Manuscript ATE_2020_177

Authors: Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado and Dr. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla

Title: Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewer. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript.

Response to Reviewer #1:

1. I recommend to put in alphabetical order the nomenclature section

The nomenclature section was completed and put in alphabetical order as suggested by the reviewer.

Corrections for Manuscript ATE_2020_177

Authors: Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado and Dr. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla

Title: Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewer. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript.

Response to Reviewer #2:

1. A kind of confusion might arise following the mention of different time steps, i.e., 10-second and 10-minute time interval. For example, it is mentioned in line 280 that “The DNI in each time step is interpolated as the TMY provides 10-min data resolution”. The abstract says “This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an annual assessment of power and freshwater production of CSP+D plants, basing on a very accurate solar field model that takes meteorological data with time steps lower than 10 seconds”. The authors may attempt to clarify and remove possible ambiguity like this.

We agree with the reviewer that the explanation about the time step used is confused. The solar field model uses time steps lower than 10 seconds but the time step of the meteorological data obtained by Meteonorm software is 10 min. Therefore, in order to use the meteorological data as inputs of the solar field model, these data are interpolated to have 10-seconds data.

The abstract and Section 2.5 have been modified to clarify this issue.

2. Although the authors emphasized that their work is distinctive from previous works because it is based on accurate data, they did not elaborate on this on their discussion and how their results are different from other previous works. The interested reader is curious to see how these results are different from others and whether or not the use of very detailed data is justified.

We would like to emphasize that all the previous works performed by the authors of this paper in CSP+D so far have been done for a design-point and any work that show annual simulation results of different CSP+D configurations at different locations had been performed before. The authors had been working on the development of partial-load models of the desalination plants in order to be integrated into an annual simulation tool, whose works were already published and cited in this paper. Also, the authors worked in the implementation of models (already developed by other authors) that simulate the partial load of the solar field and power block to be also integrated

into the annual simulation tool. We believe that an annual simulation tool is essential to obtain accurate results that allow to perform reliable financial analyses.

Therefore, the results shown in this paper are different from the ones presented so far and cannot be compared in the discussion. We have clearly defined the novelty of this paper in the Introduction Section, explaining better the differences between the works presented so far and the work presented in this paper and highlighting its importance to perform accurate economic analyses that allows a precise selection of the best CSP+D configuration according to the location.

3. The Nomenclature section is not comprehensive. For example, some acronyms like FWH1-FWH6, PHX1-PHX2, DEA in the schematics for the process are not included. Make sure to include all mentioned acronyms. See for example the symbols and subscripts included in Figure 2 (control flowchart)

We agree with the reviewer that the nomenclature section is not comprehensive. We have completed this section and put in alphabetical order. Also, as we have included an Appendix with the main equations of the models, the corresponding nomenclature has been also added in this Appendix.

4. Reconcile the reported numbers of 1990 and 1925 kW-h/m²year DNI for Almería and Abu Dhabi (lines 141-144) with those in Figure 1 (probably one sentence is needed to show how these average numbers can be obtained)

Thanks for the suggestion. The values of 1990 and 1925 kWh/m²year for Almería and Abu Dhabi, respectively, had been included just to give an idea of the average solar irradiation in those locations. However, the DNI data that are used for the solar field model are the ones shown in Fig. 1 (DNI, W/m²). Therefore, in order to avoid misunderstandings, the average values have been deleted and the following sentence has been added in Section 2:

“The Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) of both locations has been obtained using Meteornom software and the resulting hourly Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) along the year for Almería and Abu Dhabi are shown in Fig. 1”.

5. In lines 166-169, the authors state “A mathematical model, able to predict the operation at nominal and part load conditions, has been developed and implemented within Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software environment [36]. More details of this model and of the solar field are described in Ref. [37]”. The authors are recommended to summarize the algorithm of solution (probably in a clear flowchart) that describes the approach of solution followed. The same applies to the desalination blocks where a flowchart summarizing the computational algorithm is in order.

We agree with the reviewer that information about the algorithm of solutions of each model are needed to better understand the simulation tool. Therefore, a significant improvement has been done in Section 2.1, including a general flow chart that explains the interconnections between the components of a CSP+D system and the inputs needed for each model, a flow

chart of the algorithm of solution of the solar field, an explanation of the algorithm of solution of the power block model and a clearer flow chart of the loops implemented in the desalination models. Also, for the RO model, a flow chart that explains the operational strategy followed has been added. Finally, the main equations of the models of each component has been included in an Appendix.

6. The authors state in lines 222-223 “In the case of the RO plant, an operational strategy consisting in adapting the power fluctuation to the operation of the RO unit has been implemented. More details can be found in [33]”. The authors are asked to present a brief summary of that strategy and referring the details to the reference.

As explained in the previous answer, a flow chart that explains the operational strategy followed in the RO model has been added in Section 2.1. Also, the following paragraph that explains the operational strategy has been included:

“It starts evaluating P_{min} , which is the minimum power required by the RO unit to operate with the total number of pressure vessels established in the design. When the power supplied by the turbine is lower than P_{min} , the RO unit operates within a safe range (called self-operation window), varying the freshwater production according to the power availability. When the power supplied is lower than P_{min} , some pressure vessels are disabled and the fresh water production will change according to the number of the active pressure vessels”.

7. The sentences in lines 265-269 which read as “For the comparison of this system with respect to the other MED configurations, it has been established that the power block (PB) of the CSP+RO system produces the same electricity than the PB of the CSP+MED system. Then, the difference between the electricity generated by the PB and the one generated by the CSP+MED configurations is used to feed the RO unit to produce freshwater” in not clear and needs to be rephrased.

We have rephrased the sentences as follows:

In the case of the RO plant, a comparison of the CSP+RO system with respect to the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+MED-TVC systems is carried out. For that, it has been established that the CSP+RO system produces the same net power as the CSP+MED system (LT-MED or MED-TVC, according to the case). Then the rest of the generated power from the CSP+RO plant is devoted to freshwater production through the RO trains

Also, these sentences have been moved from Section 2.4 to 2.5, where the simulation procedure is explained.

8. Although overall, the manuscript is well written, editorial review is needed. See for example sentences in lines: 18, 19, 68, 112, 114, 172, 267, 287, 400, and line 6 in the Abstract.

Ambiguous sentences have been amended and the whole document has been proofread.

Corrections for Manuscript ATE_2020_177

Authors: Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado and Dr. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla

Title: Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewer. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript.

Response to Reviewer #3:

1. In introduction author totally ignored the latest hybrid desalination systems such as RO+MSF, MEDAD, MED+MSF etc.

Thanks for the suggestion. We have included two references in Introduction Section about a MED+RO hybrid system coupled to a CSP plant. The rest of works found in the literature (MEDAD, RO+MSF, MED+MSF) have not been included since they do not include the integration into a CSP plant and are thus out of the scope of this work.

2. At Figure 3, author should write state properties (P, T & flow rate) of each stream. Similar for Figure 5, 6 etc.

We would like to clarify that those figures are in Methods Section and explain the integration between the desalination unit and the CSP plant. No results of the state properties have been included in them because the results are obtained for the whole year and not for a design point. However, the authors have included a Table in Appendix A where the values of the state variables at nominal conditions are shown.

3. Author should write detail mathematical modeling equations. There is no equation currently in the manuscript and article presenting the simulation results

Although we cited in the paper the references where the equations of all models are shown, we believe that the main equations should be included in this paper for the readers' interest. Therefore, an Appendix with the main equations has been added and the corresponding nomenclature has been included.

4. In Table 1, author presented KWh/m³ for MED in the range of 30-50. These are not realistic calculations. Author mixed the electricity and low grade bleed steam in typical CCGT arrangement. Author should read related article and understand the concept of exergy of extraction steam and correct the number accordingly.

We would like to clarify that the values shown in Table 1 are only referred to the specific thermal energy consumption of the only-MED plants (not integrated into the CSP plant). The authors had provided the data of each MED unit (LT-MED and TVC-MED) at nominal conditions, just to give an idea of their characteristics. However, this table has been slightly modified and only the inputs values needed for the operational models of both desalination plants are given, so the specific thermal consumptions have been removed because they are not inputs.

5. What DNI and GWI considered in the simulation?

Due to the use of Concentrating Solar Thermal Technologies in the Power Plant, the DNI is the only useful component of the solar radiation and has been the only one used for the solar field model. The DNI of each location (Almería and Abu Dhabi) has been obtained by generating a Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) using Meteornom software. The resulting hourly DNI along the year for each location are shown in Fig. 1 of Section 2. The sentences referred to this point have been modified as follows:

“Two locations have been selected to perform the simulations: Almería (longitude 2.22W and latitude 37.06N, in Spain, representative of Southern Europe) and Abu Dhabi (longitude 54.36E and latitude 24.46N, in UAE, representative of Middle East).

The Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) of both locations has been obtained using Meteornom software and the resulting hourly Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) along the year for Almería and Abu Dhabi are shown in Fig. 1.”

6. During CSP+LT+MED, why electricity production also reduced?, in Figure 9.

It is due to the fact that the exhaust steam leaves at a higher temperature than in an only-CSP plant. It leaves at 70 °C (in an only-CSP plant the steam temperature is between 42-50 °C) to match the operating temperature of a LT-MED plant at the first effect.

It has been better clarified in Section 2.1., as follows:

“The temperature of the exhaust steam has been fixed at 70 °C to match the operating temperature of the LT-MED unit, despite the penalty caused in the electricity production due to the higher exhaust steam temperature compared to an only-CSP plant.”

7. What is the typical electricity consumption of RO?

We have considered a specific electricity consumption (SEC) for the RO unit of 5 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Abu Dhabi and 4 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Almería, taken from reference [40], as indicated in Section 2.5.

[40] J. Kim, K. Park, D.R. Yang, S. Hong, A comprehensive review of energy consumption of seawater reverse osmosis desalination plants, *Appl. Energy.* 254 (2019).
doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113652.

8. What is typical efficiency of CSP plant?

We are a bit confused about the question. If the reviewer is referring to the typical efficiency of the power block of an only-CSP plant (without desalination), the answer is 38% for the case of parabolic trough CSP plants, and up to 44% in the case of central receiver CSP plants. The solar-to-electric efficiency is around 15% (Islam et al. 2018).

M.T. Islam et al. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 91 (2018) 987–1018

9. The Specific energy presented in Figure 12 are not correct. There should be proper analysis based on primary energy as there are two different types of energy, thermal and electricity, are involved. Author should read J. Appl. Phys. 105, 044911 (2009); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3081637> (I. Dincer) to understand the specific energy concept for solar energy.

We would like to clarify that the values presented in Figure 12 (Figure 15 in the new version) correspond to the specific electric consumption (SEC), and not to the specific energy consumption. Therefore, the values shown in Figure 15 are referred only to the electricity consumed by the RO divided by the freshwater produced. Note that the lines corresponding to the LT-MED case (red and purple) are horizontal since they do not depend on the specific electric consumption of the RO unit.

10. As author mentioned LT-MED but it is not really a LT. Author can read these article to understand the LT-MED operation.

Muhammad Wakil Shahzad, Kyaw Thu, Yong-deuk Kim, Kim C Ng, An Experimental Investigation on MEDAD Hybrid Desalination Cycle, Applied Energy 148 (2015) 273–281.

We would like to highlight that Low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) is a well-established nomenclature in the scientific literature by several authors to distinguish between MED plants where the external heat source directly powers the first effect of the MED plant and the rest of configurations where an MED is coupled to a heat pump (MED-TVC, ABS-MED, MEDAD). In the last case, the external heat source directly powers the heat pump and the thermal heat coming from the heat pump powers the first effect of the MED unit.

11. Overall English need to improve.

Ambiguous sentences have been amended and the whole document has been proofread

Corrections for Manuscript ATE_2020_177

Authors: Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado and Dr. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla

Title: Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewer. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript.

Response to Reviewer #4:

As can be seen in the below papers which has been previously published by the authors of submitted manuscript (Palenzuela), there are plenty of valuable papers that have been presented by the authors regarding the dual purpose solar electricity/water systems especially for two locations of Almeria and Abu Dhabi. However, I see no novelty in the newly submitted manuscript neither in the results nor in the method. The results are not interesting and I do not believe that this paper should be considered for being published in ATE and recommend irrevocably reject the paper for further consideration.

[1] Delgado. B.O, Palenzuela. P, D.C.A. Padilla, Parametric study of a multi-effect distillation plant with thermalvapor compression for its integration in to a Rankine cycle power block, Desalination Vol 394(2016)18-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2016.04.020>

[2] P. Palenzuela, G. Zaragoza, D. Alarcón-Padilla, E. Guillén, M. Ibarra and J. Blanco, Assessment of different configurations for combined parabolic-trough (PT) solar power and desalination plants in arid regions, Energy 2011;36(8): 4950-4958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2011.05.039>.

[3] P. Palenzuela, G. Zaragoza, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, J. Blanco. Simulation and evaluation of the coupling of desalination units to parabolic-trough solar power plants in the Mediterranean region. Desalination 2011;281:379-387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.08.014>.

[4] P. Palenzuela, G. Zaragoza, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, J. Blanco. Evaluation of cooling technologies of concentrated solar power plants and their combination with desalination in the Mediterranean area. Applied Thermal Engineering, 2013; 50: 1514-1521.

We would like to emphasize that all the previous works performed by the authors of this paper in CSP+D so far have been done for a design-point and no work that show annual simulation results of different CSP+D configurations at different locations had been performed before. The authors had been working on the development of partial-load models of the desalination plants in order to be integrated into an annual simulation tool, whose works were already published and cited in this paper. Also, the authors worked in the implementation of models

(already developed by other authors) that simulate the partial load of the solar field and power block to be also integrated into the annual simulation tool. We believe that an annual simulation tool is essential to obtain accurate results that allow to perform reliable financial analyses.

We have clearly defined the novelty of this paper in the Introduction Section, explaining better the differences between the works presented so far and the work presented in this paper and highlighting its importance to perform accurate economic analyses that allows a precise selection of the best CSP+D configuration according to the location.

DATE 27th March 2020
SUBJECT Revision requested for ATE_2020_177
TITLE Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

Dr. Bansal
Editor in chief
Applied Thermal Engineering

Dear *Dr. Bansal*,

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewers. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript. The manuscript "Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study", wrote by Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado and Dr. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla, has been modified according to all the suggestions made by the reviewers. All the changes have been highlighted in yellow. We forgot to put the track changes on when we did the modifications but the changes can be distinguished clearly since they are highlighted in yellow. Regarding your comments, the answers are summarized below:

We have clearly defined the novelty of this paper in the Introduction Section, explaining better the differences between the works presented so far and the work presented in this paper and highlighting its importance to perform accurate economic analyses that allows a precise selection of the best CSP+D configuration according to the location. Likewise, we have included some references about hybrid desalination systems (MED+RO) integrated into CSP plants recommended by one of the reviewers. However, the references recommended by the reviewer related to hybrid systems MEDAD, RO+MSF, MED+MSF found in the literature have not been included since they do not include the integration into a CSP plant and are thus out of the scope of this work.

We look forward to receive your comments on the revised document.

Yours faithfully

Patricia Palenzuela

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Comparative assessment of the annual electricity and water production by Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination plants: A case study

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Abstract

The dual production of power and freshwater by the combination of Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants and desalination units, technology known as CSP+D, may help to solve the energy and water scarcity problems in arid and semi-arid regions. The lack of accurate annual analyses, crucial for the proper selection of the best CSP+D configuration, hampers the investment in this technology that has not been implemented on an industrial scale so far. This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an annual assessment of power and freshwater production of CSP+D plants, based on a very accurate solar field model that uses time steps of 10 seconds. Three CSP+D configurations have been analyzed in two different locations, Abu Dhabi (UAE) and Almería (Spain). Two of the three CSP+D configurations consider the multi-effect distillation (MED) technology for freshwater production, in low-temperature and thermocompression modes. The latter also accounts for the water and electricity demands for the selection of the best coupling arrangement. The annual results of the CSP+MED systems have been finally compared with those obtained from the third configuration, a Reverse Osmosis (RO) unit connected to a CSP plant. Results obtained indicate that, in both locations, the configuration leading to maximum water and electricity productions is CSP+RO (26% more

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26 of freshwater in Almería and 10% more in Abu Dhabi). Only if the specific energy consumption
27 of the RO process is above 5.4-5.6 kWh/m³, the most optimum configuration would be
28 CSP+MED at low temperature.

29 **Keywords:** Simulation tool; Annual operation; CSP+D; Multi-effect distillation; Reverse
30 Osmosis

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121 **1. Introduction**
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123

124 32 The water shortage is becoming a **very** serious threat to many countries. Seawater desalination
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126 33 is among the best technological solutions to provide freshwater from seawater. However, this
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128 34 solution becomes unsustainable and economically unfeasible if the **desalination** plants only rely
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130 35 on the use of fossil energy sources, which are increasingly becoming expensive and scarce.
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132 36 There is a clear nexus between energy and water that makes the coupling between desalination
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134 37 processes and solar energy technologies a real alternative for fossil fuel-powered desalination.
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136 38 The joint production of electricity and freshwater by Concentrating Solar Power and
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138 39 Desalination plants (known as CSP+D) is presented as an alternative of great interest because
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140 40 of the inherent synergy existing between both systems and due to the already known
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142 41 geographical coincidence between regions that suffer from water stress (having easy access to
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144 42 the sea) and have high levels of solar irradiation over the year.

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146 43 One of the main issues in CSP+D is the choice of the adequate desalination technology (thermal
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148 44 desalination processes such as Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) or mechanical desalination
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150 45 processes such as Reverse Osmosis (RO)) to be coupled with the CSP plant. The selection of
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152 46 the best CSP+D option depends on many factors, and it is **essential to perform** an accurate
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154 47 assessment of the annual **performance** of power and water that allows a reliable financial
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156 48 analysis, useful to predict the production costs and the feasibility of the project. Given the
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158 49 inherent variability and intermittence of the solar resource, suitable tools that simulate the
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160 50 yearly freshwater and power production accurately, considering the electricity and water
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162 51 demands of the location, are a **requirement**.

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164 52 The majority of the studies **of CSP+D** found in the literature so far **(in which the desalination**
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166 53 **plant can be MED, RO, or hybrid MED-RO)** have **been developed for a design point (i.e.,**
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168 54 **nominal conditions)** for both the desalination and the CSP systems [1-15]. **However, these**
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170 55 **design-point studies provide inaccurate results to perform economic analyses of CSP+D**

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180 56 systems, which is essential to decide the best integration scheme according to the selected
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182 57 location. A few papers based on transient models to simulate the yearly production of power
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184 58 and water can be found in the literature. Casimiro et al. [16] developed a new tool in TRNSYS
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186 59 to simulate the cogeneration of water and electricity with CSP and a Forward Feed MED (FF-
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188 60 MED) plant in San Diego (US). However, one of the main limitations of this transient model is
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190 61 in the desalination unit, which is a design model (i.e., one of the resulting outputs from the
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192 62 model is the heat transfer area of the effects) and only simulates the operation of the plant under
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194 63 nominal conditions. Mata-Torres et al. [17] also presented a model developed in TRNSYS of a
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196 64 cogeneration system consisting of a MED plant coupled with a parabolic trough CSP plant. As
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198 65 in the previously mentioned research work, the desalination model was also developed for
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200 66 design purposes (heat transfer area as an output of the model), and it is considered a steady-
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202 67 state operation of the integrated system thanks to the energy provided by the thermal storage
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204 68 and backup system. Other research works have been focused on annual simulations of CSP+D
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206 69 systems with the aim of assessing on the water and electricity costs. Calise et al. [18] presented
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208 70 a thermoeconomic analysis of a polygeneration plant that produces space heating and cooling,
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210 71 domestic hot water and drinkable desalinated water by a multi-effect distillation plant, using
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212 72 solar energy as the primary energy source by means of either linear Fresnel reflectors or
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214 73 evacuated-tube solar collectors. The polygeneration plant was simulated in TRNSYS, and a
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216 74 short time-step was used (0.02 h). The desalination unit was modeled to operate under nominal
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218 75 conditions since an auxiliary biomass-fired heater was used to supply the heat required by the
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220 76 MED unit in case of low availability of solar radiation. Hoffmann and Dall [19] reported a
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222 77 feasibility study for the integration of a multi-effect distillation plant with a central receiver
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224 78 CSP plant in Namibia. The model of the desalination unit was a steady-state design model, and
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226 79 the CSP plant was modeled assuming a one-hour time step. Askari and Ameri [20] developed
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228 80 an economic analysis to determine the water and electricity costs of a combined Linear Fresnel
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81 CSP plant with a MED. In this case, the desalination unit operates all the time under nominal
82 conditions due to the use of an auxiliary natural gas boiler, and also a one-hour time step was
83 considered for the simulation of the solar field. In the previous works, nothing is mentioned
84 about the model of the power block. Hassabou et al. [21] carried out a techno-economic
85 assessment of a Multi-Stage Flash (MSF) unit coupled with a parabolic trough CSP plant
86 located at Mersa Matruh (Egypt) as a case study for the MENA (the Middle East & North
87 Africa) region. For this purpose, transient simulations with variable operation and changing
88 weather conditions were performed throughout a year. In the case of the solar system, a time
89 and space-dependent model was developed to simulate its performance. However, as in the
90 previous research works, a full-load operation of a MSF desalination unit during a whole year
91 was assumed since the support by an additional natural gas heater during low irradiance and
92 cloudy days was considered. There are also works that determine the water and electricity costs
93 but using an exergoeconomic analysis in order to identify the thermodynamic irreversibilities.
94 Wellmann et al. [22] and Leiva-Illanes et al. [23,24] presented exergy cost assessments, but no
95 information about the governing physical equations of the different components of the
96 polygeneration system is given. Usually, these models assume a one-hour time step in the CSP
97 model due to the complexity of the exergetic analysis as in the previously mentioned research
98 works. This time step provides less accurate annual results due to the variability of solar
99 irradiance that can occur within that one-hour interval at certain times of the year. Besides, all
100 of them assume design desalination models instead of partial load models that simulate their
101 behavior under solar radiation variation. A few time-dependent MED models can be found in
102 the literature [25–29], but they aim to regulate the response of the main operational variables
103 against certain disturbances and are thus not suitable for yearly simulations of complex systems
104 such as CSP+MED plants.

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298 106 Apart from the less accuracy in the CSP and desalination models of the mentioned works, none
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300 107 of them present an annual comparative analysis between the two most usual combination
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302 108 options: CSP+MED and CSP+RO. Besides, in the case of CSP+MED combination, previous
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304 109 works do not evaluate the two possible MED configurations either: Low-Temperature MED
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306 110 (LT-MED) and MED with thermocompression (MED-TVC).

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309 111 The authors of this paper have been working on the combined CSP+D systems since 2008.
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311 112 Techno-economic analyses of different CSP+MED and CSP+RO configurations have been
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313 113 performed since them ([2], [3], [6], [8], [9], [12], [13] already cited above) but, as already
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315 114 mentioned, all of them at a design point. The need to perform accurate economic analyses led
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317 115 to the development of part-load simulation models of MED and RO plants. Ortega-Delgado et
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319 116 al. [30] presented an operational model for a MED unit with thermocompression -using variable
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321 117 nozzle steam ejectors (they have higher efficiency than the conventional ones under part-load
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323 118 operation), developed in the basis of a previously designed MED plant described in Ref. [31].
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325 119 Another operational model was developed to simulate an LT-MED based in a previous design
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327 120 model described in Ref. [32]. These operational models take the heat transfer areas of the
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329 121 desalination units as inputs and include the implementation of control loops that allow keeping
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331 122 critical variables at values close to the nominal ones against changes caused by the solar
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333 123 irradiation variability. The authors also developed a simulation model of a Reverse Osmosis
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335 124 unit to predict its operation at partial load. It is described in detail in Ref. [33].
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339 125 Using the partial load desalination models and implementing partial load models of the rest of
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341 126 the components of a CSP+D plant (i.e., solar field and power block) taken from the literature,
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343 127 the authors of this paper have developed, for the first time in their knowledge, a novel annual
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345 128 simulation tool for CSP+D systems. The solar field model (taken from Llorente-García et al.
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347 129 [34]) can run yearly simulations using time steps of ten seconds in contrast with the previously
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349 130 mentioned works that use hourly steps. The tool thus allows performing accurate yearly
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357 131 simulations of CSP+D plants, accounting also for the power and freshwater demands of the
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359 132 selected location as another added benefit.
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362 133 Two CSP+MED systems have been analyzed, in low-temperature and thermocompression
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364 134 modes, in two representative locations of the Middle East and South of Europe: Abu Dhabi
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366 135 (UAE) and Almería (Spain), respectively. Their comparison with respect to a CSP+RO system
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368 136 has been performed in both cases.
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372 137 2. Methods

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375 138 A yearly simulation tool that predicts the annual operation of CSP+D systems has been
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377 139 developed integrating models of the different components of the system: CSP plant (solar field
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379 140 and power block) and desalination plant. Two locations have been selected to perform the
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381 141 simulations: Almería (longitude 2.22W and latitude 37.06N, in Spain, representative of
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383 142 Southern Europe) and Abu Dhabi (longitude 54.36E and latitude 24.46N, in UAE,
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385 143 representative of Middle East).
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388 144 The Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) of both locations has been obtained using Meteornom
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390 145 software and the resulting hourly Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) throughout a year for Almería
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392 146 and Abu Dhabi are shown in Fig. 1. Qualitatively, the DNI is higher in Almería than in Abu
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394 147 Dhabi, and therefore higher electricity and water productions are expected in this location.
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Fig. 1. Hourly DNI during the year in Almería (left) and Abu Dhabi (right).

2.1 Modelling of the components

Fig. 2 shows a flow chart of how the components of the CSP+D system are connected to each other within the simulation tool. The details of the model of each component are given from now on.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the connection of the components' models within the simulation tool.

The CSP component is composed of the solar field and the power block, with similar characteristics to those of the 50 MW_e Andasol I CSP plant (Spain). For the solar field, the parabolic trough technology has been selected. It is composed of 156 loops and produces 144 MW_{th} at nominal conditions, being oriented in N-S direction. Each loop consists of four solar collector assemblies Flagsol® SKAL-ET 150 in series, considered identical all along the

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 475 157 solar field. In addition, two molten salt tanks are used as a thermal energy storage system
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 477 158 providing up to 7.5 h of operation at design conditions. A model based on that configuration
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 479 159 developed by Llorente García et al. [34] has been used and implemented into MATLAB
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 481 160 software environment. This model is very detailed, has been validated against actual data from
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 483 161 a commercial CSP plant with a high concordance, and can run yearly simulations using time
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 485 162 steps lower than ten seconds. The inputs of the model are shown in Fig. 2, and the resolution
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 487 163 algorithm is depicted in Fig. 3. The input data is introduced to determine the solar time,
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 489 164 incidence angle, and the thermal power collected in a loop. After that, the thermal losses in the
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 491 165 collectors and pipelines are accounted for in order to calculate the HTF temperatures and useful
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 493 166 thermal power produced in the solar field. Depending on the HTF temperatures and solar
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 495 167 irradiation levels, the plant operation is selected (including the state of the thermal energy
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 497 168 storage tanks) to determine the useful thermal power sent to the power block. The main
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 499 169 equations of the model are presented in Appendix A.

Fig. 3. Flow chart of the algorithm used for simulating the solar field. Adapted from [34].

170 For the power block, a regenerative Rankine cycle with reheating and a nominal capacity of

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533
534 171 50 MW_e **have** been selected. The power block has a high and a low-pressure turbine and a total
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536 172 of six steam extractions that go to feedwater heaters (FWH). The cooling system to condense
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538 173 the exhaust steam is composed of a surface condenser and a wet cooling tower. A steam
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540 174 generator formed by a preheater, evaporator, superheater, and reheater uses the thermal power
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543 175 delivered in the solar field to generate vapor at high temperature and pressure (370 °C and
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545 176 90 bar), which is then expanded in the turbines. **A mathematical model that simulates the**
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547 177 **operation at nominal conditions was firstly developed and then, a model able to predict the**
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549 178 **operation at part load conditions, based on that presented by Montes et al. [35], was**
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551 179 **implemented within Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software environment. This software**
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553 180 **resolves a non-linear equation system using the Newton–Raphson method by a proper**
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555 181 **initialization of the variables. The model uses the characteristics of the power block at nominal**
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557 182 **conditions as input variables. These variables and their corresponding values are shown in Fig.**
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559 183 **2 and Table A2 in Appendix A, respectively. Likewise, the main equations used for this model**
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561 184 **are presented in Appendix A.**

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564 185 In the case of the desalination unit, thermal and membrane desalination technologies have been
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566 186 selected. Amongst the thermal distillation technologies, a MED has been chosen. Multi-effect
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568 187 distillation consists **of** a series of evaporation-condensation processes that take place within
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570 188 shell and tube heat exchangers, called evaporators, in a decreasing pressure profile. The only
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572 189 external energy source is required in the first evaporator, **and** the rest are driven by the vapor
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574 190 generated in the previous evaporator. As a result, the salt is separated from the water and
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576 191 consecutively, high **purity** water is finally obtained. According to the temperature level of the
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578 192 external energy source, the MED process is classified in LT-MED or MED-TVC process. In
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580 193 the first one, the temperature level of the external energy source is between 70 – 80 °C. In the
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582 194 second one, the temperature level is between 120 – 300 °C (that corresponds to the high-
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584 195 pressure steam used to drive a thermocompressor/steam ejector coupled to the MED unit). For
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the LT-MED unit, a forward-feed arrangement has been considered. The plant has been sized considering that all the exhaust steam leaving the turbine is used as the external energy source of the MED's first effect. For the MED-TVC, the design of the unit is similar to the Trapani (Italy) desalination plant configuration [36]. The design values of both MED plants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Design values of the MED plants.

Concept	LT-MED	MED-TVC
Number of effects	12	12
Thermocompressor location	-	11
Heating/motive steam pressure (bar)	0.31	45.4
Inlet seawater salinity (ppm)	35,000	40,000
Evaporator heat transfer area (m ²)	12,643	4839
Preheater heat transfer area (m ²)	1373	150
End condenser heat transfer area (m ²)	6562	2045
Capacity (m ³ /d)	33,888	10,000

In the case of the membrane-based technology, a RO plant has been selected. It consists of several pressure vessels that contain a certain number of membranes elements placed in series. The features of the RO plant at nominal conditions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Design values of the RO plant.

Concept	Value
Capacity (m ³ /day)	50,000
Number of elements	8
Number of pressure vessels	600
Applied pressure (bar)	68.71

Recovery Ratio (%)	42
Permeate concentration (g/l)	0.218

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Taking the previous design values as inputs (as indicated in Fig. 2), operational models that simulate the partial load operation of the desalination units have been developed and implemented in EES software. The main equations of these models are presented in Appendix A. It is essential to highlight that in the case of the MED plants, control loops have been implemented to adjust specific parameters when the load of the power block decreases in order to achieve a feasible operation of the desalination plants. The algorithm of the control loops can be seen in Fig. 4. It starts by taking the outputs of the design model like the number of effects (N), the location of the thermocompressor (N_{eff}), and the area of evaporators, preheaters, and end condenser (A_{evap} , A_{preh} , A_c) as inputs. Then, a control loop is defined for each MED unit type. For the MED-TVC unit, the feedwater mass flow rate is varied so that the brine salinity in the first effect is kept below a limit value (X_{max}). Also, the cooling water flow rate (q_{cw}) is controlled by varying the heating steam temperature (T_s). This can be explained as follows: on one hand, when the MED plant works at partial operation, the brine salinity increases. In this case, the control loop increases the feedwater as well to reduce the brine salinity level. On the other hand, the cooling water is fixed by the condensation of the steam in the last effect, and the increase of the feedwater can lead to unfeasible operating points. Therefore, to counteract the increment of cooling water imposed by the feedwater, a control loop that decreases the heating steam temperature when the cooling water is below a minimum value (zero in this case) is added. For the LT-MED unit, only the cooling water flow rate is controlled since in this case the heating steam temperature is fixed by the condensation of the power block at 70 °C, and the brine concentration factor never goes above the safety limit that could cause scaling problems (1.9 for a typical 35000 ppm seawater salinity [37]). The resulting concentration factor is 1.6 at

230 nominal conditions and 1.7 in the worst scenario (50% of the load in the MED unit). Finally,
 231 the algorithm checks in both cases that the load of the MED plants (LT-MED and MED-TVC)
 232 is above 50%, which has been selected as the minimum load for the operation of the desalination
 233 plant. If this condition is not fulfilled, the MED stops; in another case, if all the requirements
 234 are **reached**, the optimal feedwater mass flow rate is achieved.

237 Fig. 4. Diagram of the control loops implemented in the operational models for MED-TVC
 238 and LT-MED.

In the case of the RO plant, an operational strategy consisting on adapting the power fluctuation to the operation of the RO unit has been implemented since the best results in terms of freshwater production and water costs were found with this strategy in comparison with the usual gradual capacity strategy, as can be found in reference [33]. Fig. 5 shows a flow chart of the power fluctuation operational strategy. It starts evaluating P_{min} , which is the minimum power required by the RO unit to operate with the total number of pressure vessels established in the design. When the power supplied by the turbine is lower than P_{min} , the RO unit operates within a safe range (called self-operation window), varying the freshwater production according to the power availability. When the power supplied is lower than P_{min} , some pressure vessels are disabled, and the freshwater production will change according to the number of the active pressure vessels.

Fig. 5. Flow chart of the power fluctuation operational strategy. Adapted from [33]

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829 **2.2 Integration of the MED-TVC unit into a CSP plant**
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832 240 For the CSP+MED-TVC system, two coupling arrangements have been considered (see Fig.
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834 241 6): i) the MED-TVC unit driven by the highest pressure turbine extraction (at 45.4 bar and
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836 242 called HP2) and ii) the MED-TVC unit driven by the lowest pressure turbine extraction (at 3.63
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838 243 bar and called LP3). From the studies presented in [30,31], it was found that in periods of the
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840 244 year with high electricity demand for the considered location, the most suitable coupling
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842 245 arrangement is using low-pressure steam extraction of 3.63 bar to feed the MED-TVC unit, as
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844 246 the penalty on the electricity production was lower, despite less water was produced. On the
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846 247 contrary, in periods of the year with low electricity demand, the high-pressure steam extraction
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849 248 of 45.4 bar resulted the most suitable for increasing the water production and the efficiency of
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851 249 the desalination process, despite the electricity generation was further penalized. According to
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853 250 these results and taking into account the monthly power demand in Almería and Abu Dhabi,
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855 251 the most suitable coupling arrangement has been selected along the year, giving priority to the
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857 252 power generation with respect to the water production.

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254 **Fig. 6.** Scheme of the MED-TVC plant integrated into a CSP plant.

255 In the case of Almería, due to the lack of data **obtained at this** location, the monthly data
 256 provided by Red Eléctrica Española for Andalusia (region from which Almeria belongs) has
 257 been taken [38]. For Abu Dhabi, data from a report provided by ADWEC company has been
 258 selected [39]. The monthly power demand for both locations is presented in **Fig. 7**. It can be
 259 seen that the profiles are similar **although** in Andalusia the power demand is higher during
 260 winter.

261 **Fig. 7.** Monthly power demand profile for Andalusia region during 2015 and for Abu Dhabi
 262 during 2016 [38,39].

264 Based on the previous power demands, the coupling arrangements shown in Table 3 (MED-
 265 TVC driven by high-pressure steam extraction HP2 or low-pressure steam extraction LP3) have
 266 been established for every month in Almería and Abu Dhabi.

267 Table 3. Selection of the monthly coupling arrangement between the MED-TVC unit and CSP
 268 in Almería and Abu Dhabi as function of the monthly power demands.

Location	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
Almería	LP3	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3	LP3	LP3	LP3	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3
Abu Dhabi	HP2	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3	HP2						

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947 **2.3 Integration of an LT-MED unit into a CSP plant**
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950 271 In the case of the CSP+LT-MED system, the LT-MED is integrated into the power block taking
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952 272 all the exhaust steam from the outlet of the LP turbine (see Fig. 8) to drive the desalination unit,
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954 273 so no monthly power demand profile has been taken into account in this case. The temperature
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956 274 of the exhaust steam has been fixed at 70 °C to match the operating temperature of the LT-MED
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958 275 unit, despite the penalty caused in the electricity production due to the higher exhaust steam
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960 276 temperature compared with an only-CSP plant.
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994 279 **Fig. 8.** Scheme of the LT-MED plant integrated into the CSP plant.
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2.4 Integration of an RO unit into a CSP plant

For the CSP+RO system, no modifications of the power block have been considered since the RO takes the electricity directly from the electric generator (see Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Scheme of the RO unit connected to the CSP plant.

2.5 Yearly simulations

The simulations of the full CSP+D system have been carried out as follows (see the connection between components in Fig. 2):

- Firstly, the solar field model uses the TMY of the location to obtain the thermal power delivered to the power block during the time interval considered (monthly). This model uses time steps of 10 s but the TMY, obtained by Meteonorm software, provides DNI data with 10-min time steps, so they are interpolated to have 10-second data as inputs of the solar field model. Therefore, 8640 points are simulated for each day, which means 3,153,600 points in the whole year. From the results obtained, data points every 10 min are selected to create a vector file containing the main variables of the solar field, in particular the thermal power transferred to the steam generator train of the power block.

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1065 296 - Secondly, the thermal power in 10-min intervals obtained by the solar field simulation,
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1067 297 is introduced in an integrated PB+D model, which calls to an external procedure where
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1069 298 the model of the desalination plant is implemented. Therefore, for each step time, the
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1071 299 model solves the power block calculating the main thermodynamic variables (e.g.,
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1073 300 pressure, temperature, enthalpy) in the cycle and the electric power produced. The
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1075 301 resulting amount of steam required by the desalination unit (steam extracted from the
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1077 302 HP turbine or LP turbine in the case of the MED-TVC unit and steam at the outlet of
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1079 303 the LP turbine in the case of the LT-MED unit) is taken as input for the solving of the
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1081 304 desalination models, and then the power and freshwater production in 10-min intervals
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1083 305 are determined (see Fig. 2). In the case of the RO plant, a comparison of the CSP+RO
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1085 306 system with respect to the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+MED-TVC systems is carried out.
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1087 307 For that, it has been established that the CSP+RO system produces the same net power
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1089 308 as the CSP+MED system (LT-MED or MED-TVC, according to the case). Then, the
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1091 309 rest of the generated power from the CSP+RO plant is devoted to freshwater production
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1093 310 through the RO trains (see Fig. 2). Specific electricity consumption (SEC) for the RO
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1095 311 unit of 5 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Abu Dhabi and 4 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Almería
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1097 312 [40] have been considered. Notice that the SEC is referred mainly to the electricity
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1099 313 consumed by pumping.
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1104 314 - Finally, the daily, monthly, and yearly amounts of energy and water produced by the
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1106 315 integrated solar and desalination plants are assessed.
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1109 316 Besides the yearly electricity and freshwater production, the number of inhabitants that could
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1111 317 be fed with water and the number of households that could be supplied with the generated
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1113 318 electricity has been determined in all cases. For the number of inhabitants, average daily water
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1115 319 consumption values of 150 L [41] and 500 L [42] have been assumed for Almería and Abu
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1117 320 Dhabi, respectively. For the number of households, 4 MWh_e per household has been taken as
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321 the average electricity consumption for Almería, according to the World Energy Council and
322 20 MWh_e for Abu Dhabi [43]. The hours of operation of the integrated plant and the daylight
323 hours (the difference between the sunset and sunrise) have also been determined, which provide
324 an idea of the number of operating hours using the Thermal Energy Storage (TES). It is
325 important to note that in the case of the CSP+MED+TVC plant, the operation time of the PB
326 and MED units have been determined separately. This is because the operation of the CSP plant
327 is not linked to the MED-TVC unit, as in the case of the CSP+LT-MED configuration (both PB
328 and desalination unit operation depend on each other). For MED-TVC configuration, a
329 minimum load of 28% has been established for the PB and 50% for the desalination unit. For
330 LT-MED configuration, the same minimum load, 50%, has been considered for both the PB
331 and the desalination unit.

3. Annual operation results

3.1 CSP+MED-TVC system

Fig. 10 shows the monthly electric energy generation and freshwater produced by the CSP+MED-TVC plant in Almería and Abu Dhabi during a whole year. Fig. 11 shows the operation time of the PB and of the MED-TVC unit and the total daylight hours.

Fig. 10. Monthly electric energy generation (left) and freshwater production (right) by a CSP+MED-TVC plant during the whole year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

Fig. 11. Monthly daylight hours, operation time of the PB and of the MED unit of the CSP+MED-TVC system along the year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

From Fig. 10, it can be seen that the electricity generated and the freshwater produced by the CSP+MED-TVC system in the case of Almería have a typical bell shape, with increasing values from January to July, and decreasing values from July to December. In the case of Abu Dhabi, the distribution in the electricity and freshwater productions was more homogeneous without a significant difference between the initial and last periods and the central ones. July was the best month in the case of Almería, where electricity generation rose 80%, and the freshwater produced up to 70%. During this month, the maximum hours of operation of the CSP+MED-TVC plant were achieved (almost 600 hours). It is important to note that the large number of operating hours depicted in Fig. 11 during this month (much higher than the daylight hours) is due to the use of the TES system that can be charged during the day when there is an excess of thermal energy in the solar field. In Abu Dhabi, May and June were the best months with the maximum operating hours (400 hours). The worst results both in Almería and Abu Dhabi were found, as expected, in December, when the CSP+MED-TVC plant operated only 150 hours and 170 hours, respectively, resulting in reductions of electricity and freshwater production of about 80%.

Regarding the annual results, it was obtained that in Almería, 39,877 households and 28,988 inhabitants could be fed throughout a whole year with the power and freshwater produced by the CSP+MED-TVC plant. This CSP+D plant could theoretically supply power

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357 and water to a small urban center of Europe. In the case of Abu Dhabi, 6,487 households and
 358 7,089 inhabitants could be supplied with the electricity and freshwater, respectively, produced
 359 by the CSP+MED-TVC plant, which means that only a relatively small town could be supplied
 360 with power and water. The significant lower number of households and inhabitants in
 361 comparison with Almería is due to the higher electricity and freshwater consumptions in this
 362 location (20 MWh_e per household and 500 L per inhabitant against 4 MWh_e per household, and
 363 150 L).

364 **3.2 CSP+LT-MED system**

365 **Fig. 12** shows the monthly electricity and freshwater produced during a year in Almería and
 366 Abu Dhabi by a CSP+LT-MED system. **Fig. 13** shows the operation time of the PB and of the
 367 LT-MED unit and the total daylight hours in both locations.

368 **Fig. 12.** Monthly electric energy generation (left) and freshwater production (right) by a
 369 CSP+LT-MED plant during the whole year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

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371 **Fig. 13.** Monthly daylight hours and operation time of both the power block and of the MED
372 unit of the CSP+LT-MED system along the year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

373 As for the CSP+TVC-MED system, the electricity generation and freshwater production in
374 Almería were very high in summer months compared with those in winter the season (see **Fig.**
375 **12**). The lowest operating hours were obtained during January and December, with 120 and
376 100 hours, respectively (see **Fig. 13**). Note that the plant operates only a small fraction of the
377 total daylight hours mainly due to the low thermal energy generated in the solar field, which
378 can be explained by the low solar altitude and therefore, high incidence angle on the collectors
379 during this season of the year which in turn reduces the quantity of irradiance captured by the
380 heat receiver of the collectors. In the case of Abu Dhabi, the electricity and freshwater produced
381 by the CSP+LT-MED plant in Abu Dhabi resulted very low in January, February, and
382 December and higher in the rest of the months, without a significant variation especially from
383 July to November. The best results **obtained in** Almería were in July, with the maximum
384 operating hours (561 hours) and, therefore, with the maximum electricity and freshwater
385 production. It is because the TES system allowed extending the operation up to 7.5 hours under
386 nominal conditions. In Abu Dhabi, the most significant increase was obtained in May with
387 respect to January, which resulted in 73% in the case of electricity generation and 62% for water
388 production. The worst month for Abu Dhabi was December, with only 123 hours of operation
389 in the whole year.

390 Regarding the annual results in Almería, it was obtained that 35,668 households could be

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391 supplied with electricity and 85,636 inhabitants with freshwater produced by the CSP+LT-
392 MED plant during a whole year. This scheme produces less power than the MED-TVC case but
393 more water (three times higher), as the desalination plant is fed by a higher amount of steam
394 from the PB. It is important to highlight that the penalty in the cycle efficiency due to the
395 condensation at 70 °C only reduces 8% the power generation in comparison with the
396 CSP+MED-TVC system. In the case of Abu Dhabi, 6,081 households and 21,909 inhabitants
397 would be fed by electricity and freshwater, respectively, during the year. Here also the LT-
398 MED scheme produces three times more water with a relatively low decrease in the power
399 generation compared with the CSP+MED-TVC scheme (6 % reduction).

3.3 Comparison between CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants

401 Fig. 14 shows the comparison between CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and
402 Almería in terms of monthly freshwater production. In the case of Almería, the freshwater
403 produced by the CSP+RO plant is always higher than the one produced by the CSP+LT-MED
404 plant. The total freshwater produced during a whole year in the CSP+RO plant was 26% higher
405 than that of CSP+LT-MED.

406 In the case of Abu Dhabi, it can be seen that during most of the months, the freshwater produced
407 by the CSP+RO plant is higher than the one produced by the CSP+LT-MED plant. Only in
408 April, May, and June, the freshwater produced by the latter surpasses the one of the former. In
409 other words, the penalty in the power block's efficiency of the CSP+LT-MED system due to
410 the high exhaust steam temperature is lower during these months than the penalty of the
411 CSP+RO configuration due to the electricity consumed by the RO unit. However, it can be
412 highlighted that the annual freshwater produced by the RO configuration is only 10% higher
413 than the LT-MED configuration.

Fig. 14. Comparison between the freshwater produced by the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and Almería

414 A parametric analysis varying the SEC of the RO unit has been performed in both locations
 415 (see **Fig. 15**) in order to analyze from which value the CSP+LT-MED plant is better in terms of
 416 annual freshwater production than the CSP+RO plant. The results of Abu Dhabi showed that
 417 the CSP+LT-MED plant has a better annual freshwater production for SECs of the RO plant
 418 from 5.6 kWh/m³ onwards. In the case of Almería, the MED configuration performed better
 419 than the RO system from 5.4 kWh/m³ onwards.

Fig. 15. Annual freshwater produced by the CSP+RO and CSP+LT-MED plants for different **SEC** of the RO unit in the locations of Almería and Abu Dhabi

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3.4 Comparison between CSP+MED-TVC and CSP+RO plants

The monthly freshwater production from the CSP+RO and CSP-MED-TVC plants in Almería and Abu Dhabi is depicted in Fig. 16. As can be seen, the RO configuration produces the double of freshwater than the MED-TVC system in the case of Abu Dhabi. In Almería, the difference was much higher due to the lower specific electric consumption of the RO in comparison with the one of Abu Dhabi (4 kWh/m³ versus 5 kWh/m³). This is due to the high penalty in the electricity generation taking place in the MED-TVC configuration because of the use of a turbine extraction to feed the steam ejector. Thus, a parametric analysis varying the SEC does not make sense in this comparison study.

Fig. 16. Comparison between the freshwater produced by the CSP+MED-TVC and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and Almería.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an accurate annual assessment of power generation and freshwater production obtained from CSP+D plants in any location. Different case studies have been analyzed using this tool: three CSP+D plants in two different locations, Almería (Spain) and Abu Dhabi (UAE).

The results obtained from the annual simulations of the CSP+MED plants showed that they could operate for a maximum of roughly 600 hours in Almería and of 400 hours in Abu Dhabi

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436 during the summer season thanks to the use of the TES system, that extend the operation up to
437 7.5 extra hours. In the case of the LT-MED scheme, the freshwater production obtained was
438 three times higher than the one from the MED-TVC scheme due to the direct coupling between
439 the MED first effect and the exhaust steam from the power block. This direct coupling caused
440 a penalty in the power generation of only 8% in Almería and 6% in Abu Dhabi.

441 From the comparison between the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO configurations, it was obtained
442 that the second one was able to produce a 26% more of freshwater yearly in Almería. This result
443 indicates that the CSP+RO option is the best combination in the South of Europe. Only if the
444 SEC of the RO unit is higher than 5.4 kWh/m³, the LT-MED combination would be selected as
445 the optimum one. In the case of Abu Dhabi, only 10% more of freshwater production was
446 obtained by the annual operation of the CSP+RO plant. The operation by the LT-MED system
447 is preferred in this location when the SEC of the RO unit is higher than 5.6 kWh/m³. Both
448 situations could occur when the improvements in the investment cost or the efficiency of the
449 LT-MED were too significant to compete against RO.

450 Finally, the comparison between CSP+RO and CSP+MED-TVC plants in both locations do not
451 justify the implementation of thermal desalination integrated into a CSP plant in the case in
452 which the considered desalination system is MED-TVC.

453 **Nomenclature**

454 *Acronyms and abbreviations*

- CSP+D** Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination
- CP** Cooling pump
- CTP** Cooling Tower Pump
- DEA** Deareator

1594		
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1597	DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
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1599	FWH	Feedwater heater
1600		
1601		
1602	FF	Forward Feed
1603		
1604	FP	Feeding pump
1605		
1606		
1607	GOR	Gain Output Ratio
1608		
1609	HP	High Pressure
1610		
1611		
1612	HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
1613		
1614		
1615	HX	Heat Exchanger
1616		
1617	LP	Low Pressure
1618		
1619		
1620	LT	Low Temperature
1621		
1622	MED	Multi-effect Distillation
1623		
1624		
1625	PB	Power Block
1626		
1627	PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almería
1628		
1629		
1630	RO	Reverse Osmosis
1631		
1632	SCA	Solar Collectors Assemblies
1633		
1634		
1635	SEC	Specific Electric Consumption
1636		
1637	TVC	Thermal Vapor Compression
1638		
1639		
1640	455	<i>Greek</i>
1641		
1642		Δ Variation step
1643		
1644		
1645		η Efficiency
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1647	456	<i>Subscripts</i>
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C	Condensate
CP	Cooling pump
FP	Feeding pump
g	Generator
HP	High-pressure
LP	Low pressure
P	Pump
ref	Reference
T	Turbine

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Variables

A_c	Area of condenser, m ²
A_{ev}	Area of evaporators, m ²
A_{preh}	Area of preheaters, m ²
C_{min}	Minimum heat capacity rate, W/C
N	Number of effects
N_{eff}	Location of the thermocompressor
p_{HP2}	Pressure of steam in HP2 turbine extraction, bar
p_{LP3}	Pressure of steam in LP3 turbine extraction, bar
p_m	Motive steam pressure, bar
P_{net}	Net power produced by the power block of the CSP+D, plant, MW _e

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1714		
1715	$P_{net_onlyCPS}$	Net power produced by the power block of the CSP plant (without desalination), MW _e
1716		
1717	$P_{Q,SF}$	Thermal power produced by the solar field, MW _{th}
1718		
1719		
1720	$P_{Q,tot}$	Total thermal power added in the power block, MW _{th}
1721		
1722	q_{cw}	Rejected cooling seawater mass flow rate, kg/s
1723		
1724		
1725	$q_{cw,lim}$	Limit value of the rejected cooling seawater mass flow rate, kg/s
1726		
1727	q_D	Distillate flow rate, m ³ /day
1728		
1729		
1730	q_F	Feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
1731		
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1733	$q_{F,nom}$	Nominal value of the feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
1734		
1735	$q_{F,opt}$	Optimum value of the feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
1736		
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1738	q_{HP2}	Mass flow rate of steam from HP2 turbine extraction, kg/s
1739		
1740	q_{LP3}	Mass flow rate of steam from LP3 turbine extraction, kg/s
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1743	q_m	Motive steam mass flow rate, kg/s
1744		
1745	q_v	Mass flow rate of vapour in the power block, kg/s
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1748	T_{ls1}	Temperature of live steam vapor entering HP turbine, °C
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1750	T_{in}	Inlet cooling seawater to end condenser, °C
1751		
1752		
1753	T_{intake}	Intake cooling seawater temperature, °C
1754		
1755	T_{pipe}	HTF temperature at the outlet of the solar field, °C
1756		
1757		
1758	T_s	Heating steam temperature, °C
1759		
1760	TTD	Terminal temperature difference, °C
1761		
1762		
1763	UA	Heat exchanger constant, kW/m ² °C
1764		
1765	\dot{W}_e	Electrical power produced in the power block, MW
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1770		

X_1 Brine salinity in the MED first effect, ppm

X_{intake} Salinity of the intake seawater, ppm

X_{max} Maximum brine salinity in the MED first effect, ppm

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461 the SOLTERMIN project (Ref. ENE2017-83973-R).

464 Appendix A

465 A.1 Solar field

468 Table A1. Representative equations of solar field model [34].

Equation	Comment
$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{1 - [\cos(\alpha_s - \beta_{tilt}) - \cos(\beta_{tilt})\cos(\alpha_s)(1 - \cos(\gamma_s - \gamma_{col}))]^2} \right)$	Incidence angle
$\eta_{opt,0} = \rho \cdot \tau \cdot \alpha \cdot f_{apLength} \cdot f_{assembly}$	Optical efficiency
$K_{iam}(\theta) = 1 - \frac{b_1\theta + b_2\theta}{\cos\theta}$	Incidence angle modifier [44]

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472 A.2 Power block

474 Table A2. Main parameters of the power block at nominal conditions [35].

Parameter	Value
<i>Turbines</i>	
HP inlet temperature (°C)	370
HP inlet pressure (bar)	90
High pressure turbine efficiency (%)	85.5
Low pressure turbine efficiency (%)	89.5
Electro-mechanical efficiency (%)	98
<i>Condenser</i>	

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Pressure (bar)	0.08
<i>Extraction point pressures</i>	
Extraction line HP2 (bar)	45.4
Extraction line HP1 (bar)	20.6
Extraction line DEA (bar)	8.75
Extraction line LP3 (bar)	3.627
Extraction line LP2 (bar)	1.224
Extraction line LP1 (bar)	0.3461

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Table A3. Main power block model equations [35].

Equation	Comment
$\frac{p_1^2 - p_2^2}{p_{1,ref}^2 - p_{2,ref}^2} = \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Pressure calculation. <i>Law of the Ellipse</i> of Stodola
$\eta_T \text{ reduction} = 0.191 - 0.409 \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right) + 0.218 \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Turbine efficiency reduction
$\eta_{gen} = 0.908 + 0.258 \cdot Load - 0.3 \cdot Load^2 + 0.12 \cdot Load^3$	Electric generator efficiency
$\frac{UA}{UA_{ref}} = \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^{0.8}$	UA factor calculation
$\frac{\eta_P}{\eta_{P,ref}} = e_{m,ref} + 2(1 - e_{m,ref}) \frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} - (1 - e_{m0}) \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Pumps efficiency calculation

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A.3 LT-MED

Table A4. Main LT-MED model equations [32].

Equation	Comment
$q_s \lambda_s + q_F h_{preh2} = (1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' + q_{B1} h_{B1}$	Energy balance in the first effect
$\dot{Q}_1 = q_F \bar{c}_{p1} (T_1 - t_{preh1}) + q_{D1} \lambda_{V1} = A_{ev1} U_{e1} (T_s - T_1)$	Heat transfer equation in the first evaporator
$q_F \bar{c}_{p,preh1} (t_{preh1} - t_{preh2}) = \alpha_1 q_{T1} \lambda_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} \bar{c}_{p,BPE1} (T_{V1}' - T_{Vsat1})$	Energy balance in preheater 1
$q_{C1} h_{C1}'' + (1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{C1}' + \alpha_2 q_{T2} h_{C2}' = q_{FB2} h_{V2}'' + q_{C2} h_{C2}''$	Energy balance in flash box 2

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A.4 MED-TVC

Table A5. Main MED-TVC model equations [31].

Equation	Comment
$q_s \lambda_s + q_s \bar{c}_{ps,sh}(T_{s,sh} - T_s) + q_{F1} h_{preh2} + q_{FB1} h_{V1}'' = (1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' + q_{B1} h_{B1}$	Energy balance in the first effect
$\dot{Q}_1 = q_{F1} \bar{c}_{p1}(T_1 - t_{preh1}) + q_{D1} \lambda_{V1} = A_{ev1} U_{e1}(T_s - T_1)$	Heat transfer equation in the first evaporator
$\left(q_F - \sum_{k=i+1}^N q_{F,k} \right) \bar{c}_{p,preh1}(t_{preh1} - t_{preh2}) = \alpha_1 q_{T1} \lambda_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} \bar{c}_{p,BPE1}(T_{V1}' - T_{Vsat1})$	Energy balance in preheater 1
$(q_{suc} + q_{dsh}) h_{sc} + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' = q_{C1} h_{C1}'' + q_{FB1} h_{V1}''$	Energy balance in flash box 1

A.5 RO

Table A5. Main RO model equations [33]

Equation	Comment
$X_b = \frac{M_f \cdot X_F + M_b \cdot X_F}{M_b}$	Mass and salinity balance
$X_d = \frac{1}{M_d} [k_s \cdot A_s \cdot X_{av}]$	Permeate concentration
$\Delta \pi = \pi_{av} - \pi_d$	Osmotic pressure across the membrane
$\Delta p = \frac{M_d}{TCF \cdot FF \cdot A_e \cdot n_e \cdot N_v \cdot k_w} + \Delta \pi$	Pressure to be applied on the membrane
$HPP = \frac{1000 \cdot M_d \cdot \Delta p}{3600 \cdot \rho_f \cdot \eta_p}$	Required power for the high-pressure pump
$SPC = \frac{HPP}{M_d}$	Specific power consumption

Appendix Nomenclature

A_e	Membrane area, m ²
A_s	Membrane total area, m ²
b_i	Parameters of the incidence angle modifier, -
$\bar{c}_{p,preh1}$	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of feedwater between t_{preh1} and t_{preh2} , J/(kg °C)

1948			
1949			
1950	498	\bar{c}_{p1}	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of feedwater between T_1
1951			
1952	499		and t_{preh1} , J/(kg °C)
1953			
1954	500	$\bar{c}_{p,BPE1}$	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of vapor between T_{V1}'
1955			
1956	501		and T_{Vsat1} , J/(kg °C)
1957			
1958	502	$\bar{c}_{ps,sh}$	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of heating steam between
1959	503		$T_{s,sh}$ and T_s , J/(kg °C)
1960			
1961	504	e_m, e_{m0}	Parameters related to the efficiency curve of the pump, -
1962			
1963	505		
1964	506	$f_{apLength}$	Reduction of the energy absorbed by the receiver due to shadowing of the
1965			bellows
1966	507		
1967			
1968	508	$f_{assembly}$	Reduction of the energy absorbed by the receiver due to assembly errors
1969			
1970	509	FF	Fouling factor
1971	510	h_{c1}	Specific enthalpy of the condensate in evaporator 1 at T_{c1} , J/kg
1972			
1973	511	h_{Ci}'	Specific enthalpy of the condensate in preheater i at T_{Vi}' , J/kg
1974			
1975	512	h_{Ci}''	Specific enthalpy of the distillate exiting the flash box i at T_{Ci}'' , J/kg
1976			
1977	513	h_{preh2}	Specific enthalpy of the feedwater inlet in preheater 1, J/kg
1978	514	h_{sc}	Specific enthalpy of condensed steam at T_s , J/kg
1979			
1980	515	h_{V1}'	Specific enthalpy of the vapour at T_{V1}' , J/kg
1981			
1982	516	h_{Vi}''	Specific enthalpy of the vapour at T_{Vi}'' , J/kg
1983			
1984	517	K_{iam}	Incidence angle modifier, -
1985	518	k_s	Salt permeability, m ³ /(m ² ·s)
1986			
1987	519	k_w	Water permeability, m ³ /(m ² ·s·kPa)
1988	520	M_b	Brine flow rate from the RO unit, m ³ /h
1989			
1990	521	M_d	Permeate flow rate from the RO unit, m ³ /h
1991	522	M_f	Feedwater flow rate entering the RO unit, m ³ /h
1992			
1993	523	n_e	Number of elements
1994			
1995	524	N_v	Number of pressure vessels
1996			
1997	525	p	Steam pressure, Pa
1998	526	q_{B1}	Mass flow rate of brine in effect 1, kg/s
1999			
2000	527	q_{Ci}	Mass flow rate of condensate exiting flashing box i , kg/s
2001			
2002	528	q_{D1}	Mass flow rate of vapor produced by boiling in effect 1, kg/s
2003			
2004			
2005			
2006			

2007			
2008			
2009	529	q_{dsh}	Mass flow rate of water to desuperheater, kg/s
2010			
2011	530	$q_{F,k}$	Mass flow rate of feedwater entering effect k , kg/s
2012			
2013	531	q_{FBi}	Mass flow rate of vapor produced in flashing box i , kg/s
2014			
2015	532	q_s	Mass flow rate of heating steam, kg/s
2016			
2017	533	q_{suc}	Mass flow rate of entrained steam, kg/s
2018	534	q_{Ti}	Total mass flow rate of vapor in effect i , kg/s
2019			
2020	535	q_v	Mass flow rate of vapor, kg/s
2021			
2022	536	\dot{Q}_1	Heat transfer rate in evaporator 1, W
2023	537	T_{CF}	Temperature correction factor
2024			
2025	538	T_i	Temperature in effect i , °C
2026			
2027	539	T_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor in effect i , °C
2028			
2029	540	T'_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor after demister in effect i , °C
2030			
2031	541	T''_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor in flash box i , °C
2032	542	$T_{Vsat,i}$	Saturation temperature of the vapor in effect i , °C
2033			
2034	543	$T_{c,i}$	Condensation temperature in effect i , °C
2035			
2036	544	t_{prehi}	Feedwater temperature exiting preheater i , °C
2037			
2038	545	$T_{s,sh}$	Temperature of superheated steam, °C
2039	546	U_{e1}	Overall heat transfer coefficient of evaporator 1, W/(m ² °C)
2040			
2041	547	X_{av}	Average salt concentration, ppm
2042			
2043	548	X_b	Brine concentration, ppm
2044			
2045	549	X_d	Permeate concentration, ppm
2046			
2047	550	X_F	Salinity of feedwater, ppm
2048	551		
2049	552	Greek	
2050			
2051	553	α	Absorbance of the receiver, -
2052			
2053	554	α_s	Solar altitude, rad
2054			
2055	555	α_1	Mass fraction of vapor condensed in preheater 1, -
2056	556	β_{tilt}	Angle of the collector's axis to the local horizontal, rad
2057			
2058	557	γ_s	Solar azimuth, rad
2059			
2060	558	γ_{col}	Collector's orientation angle, rad
2061			
2062	559	η_T	Isentropic efficiency of the steam turbine, -
2063			
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560	η_{gen}	Efficiency of the electric generator, -
561	$\eta_{opt,0}$	Peak optical efficiency, -
562	η_P	Pump efficiency, -
563	θ	Incidence angle, rad
564	λ_s	Specific enthalpy of vaporization of water at T_s , J/kg
565	ρ	Reflectivity of the parabolic mirrors, -
566	ρ_f	Feed density, kg/m ³
567	τ	Transmissivity of the receiver glass cover, -
568	π	Osmotic pressure, kPa

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570 *Superscripts*

571	'	Conditions of the vapor/condensate after the demister
572	"	Conditions of the vapor/condensate in the flashing boxes

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Highlights

- Simulation tool that allow performing accurate yearly simulations of CSP+D plants
- Use of very accurate solar field model with time steps lower than ten seconds
- The configuration leading to maximum water and electricity productions is CSP+RO
- CSP+LT-MED would be the optimum only if the SEC of RO is above 5.4-5.6 kWh/m³

26 of freshwater in Almería and 10% more in Abu Dhabi). Only if the specific energy consumption
27 of the RO process is above 5.4-5.6 kWh/m³, the most optimum configuration would be
28 CSP+MED at low temperature.

29 **Keywords:** Simulation tool; Annual operation; CSP+D; Multi-effect distillation; Reverse
30 Osmosis

31 **1. Introduction**

32 The water shortage is becoming a very serious threat to many countries. Seawater desalination
33 is among the best technological solutions to provide freshwater from seawater. However, this
34 solution becomes unsustainable and economically unfeasible if the desalination plants only rely
35 on the use of fossil energy sources, which are increasingly becoming expensive and scarce.
36 There is a clear nexus between energy and water that makes the coupling between desalination
37 processes and solar energy technologies a real alternative for fossil fuel-powered desalination.
38 The joint production of electricity and freshwater by Concentrating Solar Power and
39 Desalination plants (known as CSP+D) is presented as an alternative of great interest because
40 of the inherent synergy existing between both systems and due to the already known
41 geographical coincidence between regions that suffer from water stress (having easy access to
42 the sea) and have high levels of solar irradiation over the year.

43 One of the main issues in CSP+D is the choice of the adequate desalination technology (thermal
44 desalination processes such as Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) or mechanical desalination
45 processes such as Reverse Osmosis (RO)) to be coupled with the CSP plant. The selection of
46 the best CSP+D option depends on many factors, and it is essential to perform an accurate
47 assessment of the annual performance of power and water that allows a reliable financial
48 analysis, useful to predict the production costs and the feasibility of the project. Given the
49 inherent variability and intermittence of the solar resource, suitable tools that simulate the
50 yearly freshwater and power production accurately, considering the electricity and water
51 demands of the location, are a requirement.

52 The majority of the studies of CSP+D found in the literature so far (in which the desalination
53 plant can be MED, RO, or hybrid MED-RO) have been developed for a design point (i.e.,
54 nominal conditions) for both the desalination and the CSP systems [1-15]. However, these
55 design-point studies provide inaccurate results to perform economic analyses of CSP+D

56 systems, which is essential to decide the best integration scheme according to the selected
57 location. A few papers based on transient models to simulate the yearly production of power
58 and water can be found in the literature. Casimiro et al. [16] developed a new tool in TRNSYS
59 to simulate the cogeneration of water and electricity with CSP and a Forward Feed MED (FF-
60 MED) plant in San Diego (US). However, one of the main limitations of this transient model is
61 in the desalination unit, which is a design model (i.e., one of the resulting outputs from the
62 model is the heat transfer area of the effects) and only simulates the operation of the plant under
63 nominal conditions. Mata-Torres et al. [17] also presented a model developed in TRNSYS of a
64 cogeneration system consisting of a MED plant coupled with a parabolic trough CSP plant. As
65 in the previously mentioned research work, the desalination model was also developed for
66 design purposes (heat transfer area as an output of the model), and it is considered a steady-
67 state operation of the integrated system thanks to the energy provided by the thermal storage
68 and backup system. Other research works have been focused on annual simulations of CSP+D
69 systems with the aim of assessing on the water and electricity costs. Calise et al. [18] presented
70 a thermoeconomic analysis of a polygeneration plant that produces space heating and cooling,
71 domestic hot water and drinkable desalinated water by a multi-effect distillation plant, using
72 solar energy as the primary energy source by means of either linear Fresnel reflectors or
73 evacuated-tube solar collectors. The polygeneration plant was simulated in TRNSYS, and a
74 short time-step was used (0.02 h). The desalination unit was modeled to operate under nominal
75 conditions since an auxiliary biomass-fired heater was used to supply the heat required by the
76 MED unit in case of low availability of solar radiation. Hoffmann and Dall [19] reported a
77 feasibility study for the integration of a multi-effect distillation plant with a central receiver
78 CSP plant in Namibia. The model of the desalination unit was a steady-state design model, and
79 the CSP plant was modeled assuming a one-hour time step. Askari and Ameri [20] developed
80 an economic analysis to determine the water and electricity costs of a combined Linear Fresnel

81 CSP plant with a MED. In this case, the desalination unit operates all the time under nominal
82 conditions due to the use of an auxiliary natural gas boiler, and also a one-hour time step was
83 considered for the simulation of the solar field. In the previous works, nothing is mentioned
84 about the model of the power block. Hassabou et al. [21] carried out a techno-economic
85 assessment of a Multi-Stage Flash (MSF) unit coupled with a parabolic trough CSP plant
86 located at Mersa Matruh (Egypt) as a case study for the MENA (the Middle East & North
87 Africa) region. For this purpose, transient simulations with variable operation and changing
88 weather conditions were performed throughout a year. In the case of the solar system, a time
89 and space-dependent model was developed to simulate its performance. However, as in the
90 previous research works, a full-load operation of a MSF desalination unit during a whole year
91 was assumed since the support by an additional natural gas heater during low irradiance and
92 cloudy days was considered. There are also works that determine the water and electricity costs
93 but using an exergoeconomic analysis in order to identify the thermodynamic irreversibilities.
94 Wellmann et al. [22] and Leiva-Illanes et al. [23,24] presented exergy cost assessments, but no
95 information about the governing physical equations of the different components of the
96 polygeneration system is given. Usually, these models assume a one-hour time step in the CSP
97 model due to the complexity of the exergetic analysis as in the previously mentioned research
98 works. This time step provides less accurate annual results due to the variability of solar
99 irradiance that can occur within that one-hour interval at certain times of the year. Besides, all
100 of them assume design desalination models instead of partial load models that simulate their
101 behavior under solar radiation variation. A few time-dependent MED models can be found in
102 the literature [25–29], but they aim to regulate the response of the main operational variables
103 against certain disturbances and are thus not suitable for yearly simulations of complex systems
104 such as CSP+MED plants.

105

106 Apart from the less accuracy in the CSP and desalination models of the mentioned works, none
107 of them present an annual comparative analysis between the two most usual combination
108 options: CSP+MED and CSP+RO. Besides, in the case of CSP+MED combination, previous
109 works do not evaluate the two possible MED configurations either: Low-Temperature MED
110 (LT-MED) and MED with thermocompression (MED-TVC).

111 The authors of this paper have been working on the combined CSP+D systems since 2008.
112 Techno-economic analyses of different CSP+MED and CSP+RO configurations have been
113 performed since them ([2], [3], [6], [8], [9], [12], [13] already cited above) but, as already
114 mentioned, all of them at a design point. The need to perform accurate economic analyses led
115 to the development of part-load simulation models of MED and RO plants. Ortega-Delgado et
116 al. [30] presented an operational model for a MED unit with thermocompression -using variable
117 nozzle steam ejectors (they have higher efficiency than the conventional ones under part-load
118 operation), developed in the basis of a previously designed MED plant described in Ref. [31].
119 Another operational model was developed to simulate an LT-MED based in a previous design
120 model described in Ref. [32]. These operational models take the heat transfer areas of the
121 desalination units as inputs and include the implementation of control loops that allow keeping
122 critical variables at values close to the nominal ones against changes caused by the solar
123 irradiation variability. The authors also developed a simulation model of a Reverse Osmosis
124 unit to predict its operation at partial load. It is described in detail in Ref. [33].

125 Using the partial load desalination models and implementing partial load models of the rest of
126 the components of a CSP+D plant (i.e., solar field and power block) taken from the literature,
127 the authors of this paper have developed, for the first time in their knowledge, a novel annual
128 simulation tool for CSP+D systems. The solar field model (taken from Llorente-García et al.
129 [34]) can run yearly simulations using time steps of ten seconds in contrast with the previously
130 mentioned works that use hourly steps. The tool thus allows performing accurate yearly

131 simulations of CSP+D plants, accounting also for the power and freshwater demands of the
132 selected location as another added benefit.

133 Two CSP+MED systems have been analyzed, in low-temperature and thermocompression
134 modes, in two representative locations of the Middle East and South of Europe: Abu Dhabi
135 (UAE) and Almería (Spain), respectively. Their comparison with respect to a CSP+RO system
136 has been performed in both cases.

137 2. Methods

138 A yearly simulation tool that predicts the annual operation of CSP+D systems has been
139 developed integrating models of the different components of the system: CSP plant (solar field
140 and power block) and desalination plant. Two locations have been selected to perform the
141 simulations: Almería (longitude 2.22W and latitude 37.06N, in Spain, representative of
142 Southern Europe) and Abu Dhabi (longitude 54.36E and latitude 24.46N, in UAE,
143 representative of Middle East).

144 The Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) of both locations has been obtained using Meteornom
145 software and the resulting hourly Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) throughout a year for Almería
146 and Abu Dhabi are shown in Fig. 1. Qualitatively, the DNI is higher in Almería than in Abu
147 Dhabi, and therefore higher electricity and water productions are expected in this location.

Fig. 1. Hourly DNI during the year in Almería (left) and Abu Dhabi (right).

148 **2.1 Modelling of the components**

149 Fig. 2 shows a flow chart of how the components of the CSP+D system are connected to each
 150 other within the simulation tool. The details of the model of each component are given from
 151 now on.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the connection of the components' models within the simulation tool.

152 The CSP component is composed of the solar field and the power block, with similar
 153 characteristics to those of the 50 MW_e Andasol I CSP plant (Spain). For the solar field, the
 154 parabolic trough technology has been selected. It is composed of 156 loops and produces
 155 144 MW_{th} at nominal conditions, being oriented in N-S direction. Each loop consists of four
 156 solar collector assemblies Flagsol® SKAL-ET 150 in series, considered identical all along the

157 solar field. In addition, two molten salt tanks are used as a thermal energy storage system
 158 providing up to 7.5 h of operation at design conditions. A model based on that configuration
 159 developed by Llorente García et al. [34] has been used and implemented into MATLAB
 160 software environment. This model is very detailed, has been validated against actual data from
 161 a commercial CSP plant with a high concordance, and can run yearly simulations using time
 162 steps lower than ten seconds. The inputs of the model are shown in Fig. 2, and the resolution
 163 algorithm is depicted in Fig. 3. The input data is introduced to determine the solar time,
 164 incidence angle, and the thermal power collected in a loop. After that, the thermal losses in the
 165 collectors and pipelines are accounted for in order to calculate the HTF temperatures and useful
 166 thermal power produced in the solar field. Depending on the HTF temperatures and solar
 167 irradiation levels, the plant operation is selected (including the state of the thermal energy
 168 storage tanks) to determine the useful thermal power sent to the power block. The main
 169 equations of the model are presented in Appendix A.

Fig. 3. Flow chart of the algorithm used for simulating the solar field. Adapted from [34].

170 For the power block, a regenerative Rankine cycle with reheating and a nominal capacity of

171 50 MW_e have been selected. The power block has a high and a low-pressure turbine and a total
172 of six steam extractions that go to feedwater heaters (FWH). The cooling system to condense
173 the exhaust steam is composed of a surface condenser and a wet cooling tower. A steam
174 generator formed by a preheater, evaporator, superheater, and reheater uses the thermal power
175 delivered in the solar field to generate vapor at high temperature and pressure (370 °C and
176 90 bar), which is then expanded in the turbines. A mathematical model that simulates the
177 operation at nominal conditions was firstly developed and then, a model able to predict the
178 operation at part load conditions, based on that presented by Montes et al. [35], was
179 implemented within Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software environment. This software
180 resolves a non-linear equation system using the Newton–Raphson method by a proper
181 initialization of the variables. The model uses the characteristics of the power block at nominal
182 conditions as input variables. These variables and their corresponding values are shown in Fig.
183 2 and Table A2 in Appendix A, respectively. Likewise, the main equations used for this model
184 are presented in Appendix A.

185 In the case of the desalination unit, thermal and membrane desalination technologies have been
186 selected. Amongst the thermal distillation technologies, a MED has been chosen. Multi-effect
187 distillation consists of a series of evaporation-condensation processes that take place within
188 shell and tube heat exchangers, called evaporators, in a decreasing pressure profile. The only
189 external energy source is required in the first evaporator, and the rest are driven by the vapor
190 generated in the previous evaporator. As a result, the salt is separated from the water and
191 consecutively, high purity water is finally obtained. According to the temperature level of the
192 external energy source, the MED process is classified in LT-MED or MED-TVC process. In
193 the first one, the temperature level of the external energy source is between 70 – 80 °C. In the
194 second one, the temperature level is between 120 – 300 °C (that corresponds to the high-
195 pressure steam used to drive a thermocompressor/steam ejector coupled to the MED unit). For

196 the LT-MED unit, a forward-feed arrangement has been considered. The plant has been sized
 197 considering that all the exhaust steam leaving the turbine is used as the external energy source
 198 of the MED's first effect. For the MED-TVC, the design of the unit is similar to the Trapani
 199 (Italy) desalination plant configuration [36]. The design values of both MED plants are shown
 200 in Table 1.

201 Table 1. Design values of the MED plants.

Concept	LT-MED	MED-TVC
Number of effects	12	12
Thermocompressor location	-	11
Heating/motive steam pressure (bar)	0.31	45.4
Inlet seawater salinity (ppm)	35,000	40,000
Evaporator heat transfer area (m ²)	12,643	4839
Preheater heat transfer area (m ²)	1373	150
End condenser heat transfer area (m ²)	6562	2045
Capacity (m ³ /d)	33,888	10,000

202

203 In the case of the membrane-based technology, a RO plant has been selected. It consists of
 204 several pressure vessels that contain a certain number of membranes elements placed in series.

205 The features of the RO plant at nominal conditions are shown in Table 2.

206 Table 2. Design values of the RO plant.

Concept	Value
Capacity (m ³ /day)	50,000
Number of elements	8
Number of pressure vessels	600
Applied pressure (bar)	68.71

Recovery Ratio (%)	42
Permeate concentration (g/l)	0.218

207

208 Taking the previous design values as inputs (as indicated in Fig. 2), operational models that
209 simulate the partial load operation of the desalination units have been developed and
210 implemented in EES software. The main equations of these models are presented in Appendix
211 A. It is essential to highlight that in the case of the MED plants, control loops have been
212 implemented to adjust specific parameters when the load of the power block decreases in order
213 to achieve a feasible operation of the desalination plants. The algorithm of the control loops can
214 be seen in Fig. 4. It starts by taking the outputs of the design model like the number of effects (N
215), the location of the thermocompressor (N_{eff}), and the area of evaporators, preheaters, and end
216 condenser (A_{evap} , A_{preh} , A_c) as inputs. Then, a control loop is defined for each MED unit type.
217 For the MED-TVC unit, the feedwater mass flow rate is varied so that the brine salinity in the
218 first effect is kept below a limit value (X_{max}). Also, the cooling water flow rate (q_{cw}) is
219 controlled by varying the heating steam temperature (T_s). This can be explained as follows: on
220 one hand, when the MED plant works at partial operation, the brine salinity increases. In this
221 case, the control loop increases the feedwater as well to reduce the brine salinity level. On the
222 other hand, the cooling water is fixed by the condensation of the steam in the last effect, and
223 the increase of the feedwater can lead to unfeasible operating points. Therefore, to counteract
224 the increment of cooling water imposed by the feedwater, a control loop that decreases the
225 heating steam temperature when the cooling water is below a minimum value (zero in this case)
226 is added. For the LT-MED unit, only the cooling water flow rate is controlled since in this case
227 the heating steam temperature is fixed by the condensation of the power block at 70 °C, and the
228 brine concentration factor never goes above the safety limit that could cause scaling problems
229 (1.9 for a typical 35000 ppm seawater salinity [37]). The resulting concentration factor is 1.6 at

230 nominal conditions and 1.7 in the worst scenario (50% of the load in the MED unit). Finally,
 231 the algorithm checks in both cases that the load of the MED plants (LT-MED and MED-TVC)
 232 is above 50%, which has been selected as the minimum load for the operation of the desalination
 233 plant. If this condition is not fulfilled, the MED stops; in another case, if all the requirements
 234 are reached, the optimal feedwater mass flow rate is achieved.

235

236

237 Fig. 4. Diagram of the control loops implemented in the operational models for MED-TVC
 238 and LT-MED.

In the case of the RO plant, an operational strategy consisting on adapting the power fluctuation to the operation of the RO unit has been implemented since the best results in terms of freshwater production and water costs were found with this strategy in comparison with the usual gradual capacity strategy, as can be found in reference [33]. Fig. 5 shows a flow chart of the power fluctuation operational strategy. It starts evaluating P_{min} , which is the minimum power required by the RO unit to operate with the total number of pressure vessels established in the design. When the power supplied by the turbine is lower than P_{min} , the RO unit operates within a safe range (called self-operation window), varying the freshwater production according to the power availability. When the power supplied is lower than P_{min} , some pressure vessels are disabled, and the freshwater production will change according to the number of the active pressure vessels.

Fig. 5. Flow chart of the power fluctuation operational strategy. Adapted from [33]

239 **2.2 Integration of the MED-TVC unit into a CSP plant**

240 For the CSP+MED-TVC system, two coupling arrangements have been considered (see Fig.
 241 6): i) the MED-TVC unit driven by the highest pressure turbine extraction (at 45.4 bar and
 242 called HP2) and ii) the MED-TVC unit driven by the lowest pressure turbine extraction (at 3.63
 243 bar and called LP3). From the studies presented in [30,31], it was found that in periods of the
 244 year with high electricity demand for the considered location, the most suitable coupling
 245 arrangement is using low-pressure steam extraction of 3.63 bar to feed the MED-TVC unit, as
 246 the penalty on the electricity production was lower, despite less water was produced. On the
 247 contrary, in periods of the year with low electricity demand, the high-pressure steam extraction
 248 of 45.4 bar resulted the most suitable for increasing the water production and the efficiency of
 249 the desalination process, despite the electricity generation was further penalized. According to
 250 these results and taking into account the monthly power demand in Almería and Abu Dhabi,
 251 the most suitable coupling arrangement has been selected along the year, giving priority to the
 252 power generation with respect to the water production.

253

254 Fig. 6. Scheme of the MED-TVC plant integrated into a CSP plant.

255 In the case of Almería, due to the lack of data obtained at this location, the monthly data
 256 provided by Red Eléctrica Española for Andalusia (region from which Almeria belongs) has
 257 been taken [38]. For Abu Dhabi, data from a report provided by ADWEC company has been
 258 selected [39]. The monthly power demand for both locations is presented in Fig. 7. It can be
 259 seen that the profiles are similar although in Andalusia the power demand is higher during
 260 winter.

261
 262 Fig. 7. Monthly power demand profile for Andalusia region during 2015 and for Abu Dhabi
 263 during 2016 [38,39].

264 Based on the previous power demands, the coupling arrangements shown in Table 3 (MED-
 265 TVC driven by high-pressure steam extraction HP2 or low-pressure steam extraction LP3) have
 266 been established for every month in Almería and Abu Dhabi.

267 Table 3. Selection of the monthly coupling arrangement between the MED-TVC unit and CSP
 268 in Almería and Abu Dhabi as function of the monthly power demands.

Location	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
Almería	LP3	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3	LP3	LP3	LP3	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3
Abu Dhabi	HP2	HP2	HP2	HP2	LP3	HP2						

269

270 **2.3 Integration of an LT-MED unit into a CSP plant**

271 In the case of the CSP+LT-MED system, the LT-MED is integrated into the power block taking
272 all the exhaust steam from the outlet of the LP turbine (see Fig. 8) to drive the desalination unit,
273 so no monthly power demand profile has been taken into account in this case. The temperature
274 of the exhaust steam has been fixed at 70 °C to match the operating temperature of the LT-MED
275 unit, despite the penalty caused in the electricity production due to the higher exhaust steam
276 temperature compared with an only-CSP plant.

277

278

279 Fig. 8. Scheme of the LT-MED plant integrated into the CSP plant.

280 **2.4 Integration of an RO unit into a CSP plant**

281 For the CSP+RO system, no modifications of the power block have been considered since the
282 RO takes the electricity directly from the electric generator (see Fig. 9).

283

284 Fig. 9. Scheme of the RO unit connected to the CSP plant.

285 **2.5 Yearly simulations**

286 The simulations of the full CSP+D system have been carried out as follows (see the connection
287 between components in Fig. 2):

- 288 - Firstly, the solar field model uses the TMY of the location to obtain the thermal power
289 delivered to the power block during the time interval considered (monthly). This model
290 uses time steps of 10 s but the TMY, obtained by Meteonorm software, provides DNI
291 data with 10-min time steps, so they are interpolated to have 10-second data as inputs
292 of the solar field model. Therefore, 8640 points are simulated for each day, which means
293 3,153,600 points in the whole year. From the results obtained, data points every 10 min
294 are selected to create a vector file containing the main variables of the solar field, in
295 particular the thermal power transferred to the steam generator train of the power block.

296 - Secondly, the thermal power in 10-min intervals obtained by the solar field simulation,
297 is introduced in an integrated PB+D model, which calls to an external procedure where
298 the model of the desalination plant is implemented. Therefore, for each step time, the
299 model solves the power block calculating the main thermodynamic variables (e.g.,
300 pressure, temperature, enthalpy) in the cycle and the electric power produced. The
301 resulting amount of steam required by the desalination unit (steam extracted from the
302 HP turbine or LP turbine in the case of the MED-TVC unit and steam at the outlet of
303 the LP turbine in the case of the LT-MED unit) is taken as input for the solving of the
304 desalination models, and then the power and freshwater production in 10-min intervals
305 are determined (see Fig. 2). In the case of the RO plant, a comparison of the CSP+RO
306 system with respect to the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+MED-TVC systems is carried out.
307 For that, it has been established that the CSP+RO system produces the same net power
308 as the CSP+MED system (LT-MED or MED-TVC, according to the case). Then, the
309 rest of the generated power from the CSP+RO plant is devoted to freshwater production
310 through the RO trains (see Fig. 2). Specific electricity consumption (SEC) for the RO
311 unit of 5 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Abu Dhabi and 4 kWh/m³ of freshwater for Almería
312 [40] have been considered. Notice that the SEC is referred mainly to the electricity
313 consumed by pumping.

314 - Finally, the daily, monthly, and yearly amounts of energy and water produced by the
315 integrated solar and desalination plants are assessed.

316 Besides the yearly electricity and freshwater production, the number of inhabitants that could
317 be fed with water and the number of households that could be supplied with the generated
318 electricity has been determined in all cases. For the number of inhabitants, average daily water
319 consumption values of 150 L [41] and 500 L [42] have been assumed for Almería and Abu
320 Dhabi, respectively. For the number of households, 4 MWh_e per household has been taken as

321 the average electricity consumption for Almería, according to the World Energy Council and
 322 20 MWh_e for Abu Dhabi [43]. The hours of operation of the integrated plant and the daylight
 323 hours (the difference between the sunset and sunrise) have also been determined, which provide
 324 an idea of the number of operating hours using the Thermal Energy Storage (TES). It is
 325 important to note that in the case of the CSP+MED+TVC plant, the operation time of the PB
 326 and MED units have been determined separately. This is because the operation of the CSP plant
 327 is not linked to the MED-TVC unit, as in the case of the CSP+LT-MED configuration (both PB
 328 and desalination unit operation depend on each other). For MED-TVC configuration, a
 329 minimum load of 28% has been established for the PB and 50% for the desalination unit. For
 330 LT-MED configuration, the same minimum load, 50%, has been considered for both the PB
 331 and the desalination unit.

332 3. Annual operation results

333 3.1 CSP+MED-TVC system

334 Fig. 10 shows the monthly electric energy generation and freshwater produced by the
 335 CSP+MED-TVC plant in Almería and Abu Dhabi during a whole year. Fig. 11 shows the
 336 operation time of the PB and of the MED-TVC unit and the total daylight hours.

337 Fig. 10. Monthly electric energy generation (left) and freshwater production (right) by a
 338 CSP+MED-TVC plant during the whole year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

Fig. 11. Monthly daylight hours, operation time of the PB and of the MED unit of the CSP+MED-TVC system along the year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

339 From Fig. 10, it can be seen that the electricity generated and the freshwater produced by the
 340 CSP+MED-TVC system in the case of Almería have a typical bell shape, with increasing values
 341 from January to July, and decreasing values from July to December. In the case of Abu Dhabi,
 342 the distribution in the electricity and freshwater productions was more homogeneous without a
 343 significant difference between the initial and last periods and the central ones. July was the best
 344 month in the case of Almería, where electricity generation rose 80%, and the freshwater
 345 produced up to 70%. During this month, the maximum hours of operation of the CSP+MED-
 346 TVC plant were achieved (almost 600 hours). It is important to note that the large number of
 347 operating hours depicted in Fig. 11 during this month (much higher than the daylight hours) is
 348 due to the use of the TES system that can be charged during the day when there is an excess of
 349 thermal energy in the solar field. In Abu Dhabi, May and June were the best months with the
 350 maximum operating hours (400 hours). The worst results both in Almería and Abu Dhabi were
 351 found, as expected, in December, when the CSP+MED-TVC plant operated only 150 hours and
 352 170 hours, respectively, resulting in reductions of electricity and freshwater production of about
 353 80%.

354 Regarding the annual results, it was obtained that in Almería, 39,877 households and
 355 28,988 inhabitants could be fed throughout a whole year with the power and freshwater
 356 produced by the CSP+MED-TVC plant. This CSP+D plant could theoretically supply power

357 and water to a small urban center of Europe. In the case of Abu Dhabi, 6,487 households and
 358 7,089 inhabitants could be supplied with the electricity and freshwater, respectively, produced
 359 by the CSP+MED-TVC plant, which means that only a relatively small town could be supplied
 360 with power and water. The significant lower number of households and inhabitants in
 361 comparison with Almería is due to the higher electricity and freshwater consumptions in this
 362 location (20 MWh_e per household and 500 L per inhabitant against 4 MWh_e per household, and
 363 150 L).

364 3.2 CSP+LT-MED system

365 Fig. 12 shows the monthly electricity and freshwater produced during a year in Almería and
 366 Abu Dhabi by a CSP+LT-MED system. Fig. 13 shows the operation time of the PB and of the
 367 LT-MED unit and the total daylight hours in both locations.

368 Fig. 12. Monthly electric energy generation (left) and freshwater production (right) by a
 369 CSP+LT-MED plant during the whole year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

370

371 Fig. 13. Monthly daylight hours and operation time of both the power block and of the MED
 372 unit of the CSP+LT-MED system along the year in Almería and Abu Dhabi

373 As for the CSP+TVC-MED system, the electricity generation and freshwater production in
 374 Almería were very high in summer months compared with those in winter the season (see Fig.
 375 12). The lowest operating hours were obtained during January and December, with 120 and
 376 100 hours, respectively (see Fig. 13). Note that the plant operates only a small fraction of the
 377 total daylight hours mainly due to the low thermal energy generated in the solar field, which
 378 can be explained by the low solar altitude and therefore, high incidence angle on the collectors
 379 during this season of the year which in turn reduces the quantity of irradiance captured by the
 380 heat receiver of the collectors. In the case of Abu Dhabi, the electricity and freshwater produced
 381 by the CSP+LT-MED plant in Abu Dhabi resulted very low in January, February, and
 382 December and higher in the rest of the months, without a significant variation especially from
 383 July to November. The best results obtained in Almería were in July, with the maximum
 384 operating hours (561 hours) and, therefore, with the maximum electricity and freshwater
 385 production. It is because the TES system allowed extending the operation up to 7.5 hours under
 386 nominal conditions. In Abu Dhabi, the most significant increase was obtained in May with
 387 respect to January, which resulted in 73% in the case of electricity generation and 62% for water
 388 production. The worst month for Abu Dhabi was December, with only 123 hours of operation
 389 in the whole year.

390 Regarding the annual results in Almería, it was obtained that 35,668 households could be

391 supplied with electricity and 85,636 inhabitants with freshwater produced by the CSP+LT-
392 MED plant during a whole year. This scheme produces less power than the MED-TVC case but
393 more water (three times higher), as the desalination plant is fed by a higher amount of steam
394 from the PB. It is important to highlight that the penalty in the cycle efficiency due to the
395 condensation at 70 °C only reduces 8% the power generation in comparison with the
396 CSP+MED-TVC system. In the case of Abu Dhabi, 6,081 households and 21,909 inhabitants
397 would be fed by electricity and freshwater, respectively, during the year. Here also the LT-
398 MED scheme produces three times more water with a relatively low decrease in the power
399 generation compared with the CSP+MED-TVC scheme (6 % reduction).

400 **3.3 Comparison between CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants**

401 Fig. 14 shows the comparison between CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and
402 Almería in terms of monthly freshwater production. In the case of Almería, the freshwater
403 produced by the CSP+RO plant is always higher than the one produced by the CSP+LT-MED
404 plant. The total freshwater produced during a whole year in the CSP+RO plant was 26% higher
405 than that of CSP+LT-MED.

406 In the case of Abu Dhabi, it can be seen that during most of the months, the freshwater produced
407 by the CSP+RO plant is higher than the one produced by the CSP+LT-MED plant. Only in
408 April, May, and June, the freshwater produced by the latter surpasses the one of the former. In
409 other words, the penalty in the power block's efficiency of the CSP+LT-MED system due to
410 the high exhaust steam temperature is lower during these months than the penalty of the
411 CSP+RO configuration due to the electricity consumed by the RO unit. However, it can be
412 highlighted that the annual freshwater produced by the RO configuration is only 10% higher
413 than the LT-MED configuration.

Fig. 14. Comparison between the freshwater produced by the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and Almería

414 A parametric analysis varying the SEC of the RO unit has been performed in both locations
 415 (see Fig. 15) in order to analyze from which value the CSP+LT-MED plant is better in terms of
 416 annual freshwater production than the CSP+RO plant. The results of Abu Dhabi showed that
 417 the CSP+LT-MED plant has a better annual freshwater production for SECs of the RO plant
 418 from 5.6 kWh/m³ onwards. In the case of Almería, the MED configuration performed better
 419 than the RO system from 5.4 kWh/m³ onwards.

Fig. 15. Annual freshwater produced by the CSP+RO and CSP+LT-MED plants for different SEC of the RO unit in the locations of Almería and Abu Dhabi

420 **3.4 Comparison between CSP+MED-TVC and CSP+RO plants**

421 The monthly freshwater production from the CSP+RO and CSP-MED-TVC plants in Almería
422 and Abu Dhabi is depicted in Fig. 16. As can be seen, the RO configuration produces the double
423 of freshwater than the MED-TVC system in the case of Abu Dhabi. In Almería, the difference
424 was much higher due to the lower specific electric consumption of the RO in comparison with
425 the one of Abu Dhabi (4 kWh/m³ versus 5 kWh/m³). This is due to the high penalty in the
426 electricity generation taking place in the MED-TVC configuration because of the use of a
427 turbine extraction to feed the steam ejector. Thus, a parametric analysis varying the SEC does
428 not make sense in this comparison study.

Fig. 16. Comparison between the freshwater produced by the CSP+MED-TVC and CSP+RO plants in Abu Dhabi and Almería.

429 **4. Conclusions**

430 This paper presents a simulation tool able to perform an accurate annual assessment of power
431 generation and freshwater production obtained from CSP+D plants in any location. Different
432 case studies have been analyzed using this tool: three CSP+D plants in two different locations,
433 Almería (Spain) and Abu Dhabi (UAE).

434 The results obtained from the annual simulations of the CSP+MED plants showed that they
435 could operate for a maximum of roughly 600 hours in Almería and of 400 hours in Abu Dhabi

436 during the summer season thanks to the use of the TES system, that extend the operation up to
437 7.5 extra hours. In the case of the LT-MED scheme, the freshwater production obtained was
438 three times higher than the one from the MED-TVC scheme due to the direct coupling between
439 the MED first effect and the exhaust steam from the power block. This direct coupling caused
440 a penalty in the power generation of only 8% in Almería and 6% in Abu Dhabi.

441 From the comparison between the CSP+LT-MED and CSP+RO configurations, it was obtained
442 that the second one was able to produce a 26% more of freshwater yearly in Almería. This result
443 indicates that the CSP+RO option is the best combination in the South of Europe. Only if the
444 SEC of the RO unit is higher than 5.4 kWh/m³, the LT-MED combination would be selected as
445 the optimum one. In the case of Abu Dhabi, only 10% more of freshwater production was
446 obtained by the annual operation of the CSP+RO plant. The operation by the LT-MED system
447 is preferred in this location when the SEC of the RO unit is higher than 5.6 kWh/m³. Both
448 situations could occur when the improvements in the investment cost or the efficiency of the
449 LT-MED were too significant to compete against RO.

450 Finally, the comparison between CSP+RO and CSP+MED-TVC plants in both locations do not
451 justify the implementation of thermal desalination integrated into a CSP plant in the case in
452 which the considered desalination system is MED-TVC.

453 **Nomenclature**

454 *Acronyms and abbreviations*

CSP+D Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination

CP Cooling pump

CTP Cooling Tower Pump

DEA Deareator

DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
FWH	Feedwater heater
FF	Forward Feed
FP	Feeding pump
GOR	Gain Output Ratio
HP	High Pressure
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HX	Heat Exchanger
LP	Low Pressure
LT	Low Temperature
MED	Multi-effect Distillation
PB	Power Block
PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almería
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SCA	Solar Collectors Assemblies
SEC	Specific Electric Consumption
TVC	Thermal Vapor Compression

455 *Greek*

Δ Variation step

η Efficiency

456 *Subscripts*

C	Condensate
CP	Cooling pump
FP	Feeding pump
g	Generator
HP	High-pressure
LP	Low pressure
P	Pump
ref	Reference
T	Turbine

457

458 *Variables*

A_c	Area of condenser, m ²
A_{ev}	Area of evaporators, m ²
A_{preh}	Area of preheaters, m ²
C_{min}	Minimum heat capacity rate, W/C
N	Number of effects
N_{eff}	Location of the thermocompressor
p_{HP2}	Pressure of steam in HP2 turbine extraction, bar
p_{LP3}	Pressure of steam in LP3 turbine extraction, bar
p_m	Motive steam pressure, bar
P_{net}	Net power produced by the power block of the CSP+D, plant, MW _e

$P_{net_onlyCPS}$	Net power produced by the power block of the CSP plant (without desalination), MW_e
$P_{Q,SF}$	Thermal power produced by the solar field, MW_{th}
$P_{Q,tot}$	Total thermal power added in the power block, MW_{th}
q_{cw}	Rejected cooling seawater mass flow rate, kg/s
$q_{cw,lim}$	Limit value of the rejected cooling seawater mass flow rate, kg/s
q_D	Distillate flow rate, m^3/day
q_F	Feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
$q_{F,nom}$	Nominal value of the feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
q_{FOpt}	Optimum value of the feedwater mass flow rate, kg/s
q_{HP2}	Mass flow rate of steam from HP2 turbine extraction, kg/s
q_{LP3}	Mass flow rate of steam from LP3 turbine extraction, kg/s
q_m	Motive steam mass flow rate, kg/s
q_v	Mass flow rate of vapour in the power block, kg/s
T_{ls1}	Temperature of live steam vapor entering HP turbine, °C
T_{in}	Inlet cooling seawater to end condenser, °C
T_{intake}	Intake cooling seawater temperature, °C
T_{pipe}	HTF temperature at the outlet of the solar field, °C
T_s	Heating steam temperature, °C
TTD	Terminal temperature difference, °C
UA	Heat exchanger constant, $kW/m^2°C$
\dot{W}_e	Electrical power produced in the power block, MW

X_1	Brine salinity in the MED first effect, ppm
X_{intake}	Salinity of the intake seawater, ppm
X_{max}	Maximum brine salinity in the MED first effect, ppm

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464 Appendix A

465 A.1 Solar field

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468 Table A1. Representative equations of solar field model [34].

Equation	Comment
$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{1 - [\cos(\alpha_s - \beta_{tilt}) - \cos(\beta_{tilt})\cos(\alpha_s)(1 - \cos(\gamma_s - \gamma_{col}))]^2} \right)$	Incidence angle
$\eta_{opt,0} = \rho \cdot \tau \cdot \alpha \cdot f_{apLength} \cdot f_{assembly}$	Optical efficiency
$K_{iam}(\theta) = 1 - \frac{b_1\theta + b_2\theta}{\cos\theta}$	Incidence angle modifier [44]

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473 A.2 Power block

474 Table A2. Main parameters of the power block at nominal conditions [35].

Parameter	Value
<i>Turbines</i>	
HP inlet temperature (°C)	370
HP inlet pressure (bar)	90
High pressure turbine efficiency (%)	85.5
Low pressure turbine efficiency (%)	89.5
Electro-mechanical efficiency (%)	98
<i>Condenser</i>	

Pressure (bar)	0.08
<i>Extraction point pressures</i>	
Extraction line HP2 (bar)	45.4
Extraction line HP1 (bar)	20.6
Extraction line DEA (bar)	8.75
Extraction line LP3 (bar)	3.627
Extraction line LP2 (bar)	1.224
Extraction line LP1 (bar)	0.3461

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Table A3. Main power block model equations [35].

Equation	Comment
$\frac{p_1^2 - p_2^2}{p_{1,ref}^2 - p_{2,ref}^2} = \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Pressure calculation. <i>Law of the Ellipse</i> of Stodola
$\eta_T reduction = 0.191 - 0.409 \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right) + 0.218 \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Turbine efficiency reduction
$\eta_{gen} = 0.908 + 0.258 \cdot Load - 0.3 \cdot Load^2 + 0.12 \cdot Load^3$	Electric generator efficiency
$\frac{UA}{UA_{ref}} = \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^{0.8}$	UA factor calculation
$\frac{\eta_P}{\eta_{P,ref}} = e_{m,ref} + 2(1 - e_{m,ref}) \frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} - (1 - e_{m0}) \left(\frac{q_v}{q_{v,ref}} \right)^2$	Pumps efficiency calculation

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480 **A.3 LT-MED**

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Table A4. Main LT-MED model equations [32].

Equation	Comment
$q_s \lambda_s + q_F h_{preh2} = (1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' + q_{B1} h_{B1}$	Energy balance in the first effect
$\dot{Q}_1 = q_F \bar{c}_{p1} (T_1 - t_{preh1}) + q_{D1} \lambda_{V1} = A_{ev1} U_{e1} (T_s - T_1)$	Heat transfer equation in the first evaporator
$q_F \bar{c}_{p,preh1} (t_{preh1} - t_{preh2}) = \alpha_1 q_{T1} \lambda_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} \bar{c}_{p,BPE1} (T_{V1}' - T_{Vsat1})$	Energy balance in preheater 1
$q_{C1} h_{C1}'' + (1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{C1}' + \alpha_2 q_{T2} h_{C2}' = q_{FB2} h_{V2}'' + q_{C2} h_{C2}''$	Energy balance in flash box 2

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484 **A.4 MED-TVC**

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Table A5. Main MED-TVC model equations [31].

Equation	Comment
$q_s \lambda_s + q_s \bar{c}_{ps,sh}(T_{s,sh} - T_s) + q_{F1} h_{preh2} + q_{FB1} h_{V1}'' =$ $(1 - \alpha_1) q_{T1} h_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' + q_{B1} h_{B1}$	Energy balance in the first effect
$\dot{Q}_1 = q_{F1} \bar{c}_{p1}(T_1 - t_{preh1}) + q_{D1} \lambda_{V1} = A_{ev1} U_{e1}(T_s - T_1)$	Heat transfer equation in the first evaporator
$\left(q_F - \sum_{k=i+1}^N q_{F,k} \right) \bar{c}_{p,preh1}(t_{preh1} - t_{preh2}) =$ $\alpha_1 q_{T1} \lambda_{V1}' + \alpha_1 q_{T1} \bar{c}_{p,BPE1}(T_{V1}' - T_{Vsat1})$	Energy balance in preheater 1
$(q_{suc} + q_{dsh}) h_{sc} + \alpha_1 q_{T1} h_{C1}' = q_{C1} h_{C1}'' + q_{FB1} h_{V1}''$	Energy balance in flash box 1

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489 **A.5 RO**

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Table A5. Main RO model equations [33]

Equation	Comment
$X_b = \frac{M_f \cdot X_f + M_b \cdot X_F}{M_b}$	Mass and salinity balance
$X_d = \frac{1}{M_d} [k_s \cdot A_s \cdot X_{av}]$	Permeate concentration
$\Delta \pi = \pi_{av} - \pi_d$	Osmotic pressure across the membrane
$\Delta p = \frac{M_d}{TCF \cdot FF \cdot A_e \cdot n_e \cdot N_v \cdot k_w} + \Delta \pi$	Pressure to be applied on the membrane
$HPP = \frac{1000 \cdot M_d \cdot \Delta p}{3600 \cdot \rho_f \cdot \eta_p}$	Required power for the high-pressure pump
$SPC = \frac{HPP}{M_d}$	Specific power consumption

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492 **Appendix Nomenclature**493 A_e Membrane area, m²494 A_s Membrane total area, m²495 b_i Parameters of the incidence angle modifier, -496 $\bar{c}_{p,preh1}$ Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of feedwater between497 t_{preh1} and t_{preh2} , J/(kg °C)

498	\bar{c}_{p1}	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of feedwater between T_1
499		and t_{preh1} , J/(kg °C)
500	$\bar{c}_{p,BPE1}$	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of vapor between T_{V1}'
501		and T_{Vsat1}' , J/(kg °C)
502	$\bar{c}_{ps,sh}$	Average specific heat capacity at constant pressure of heating steam between
503		$T_{s,sh}$ and T_s , J/(kg °C)
504	e_m, e_{m0}	Parameters related to the efficiency curve of the pump, -
505		
506	$f_{apLength}$	Reduction of the energy absorbed by the receiver due to shadowing of the
507		bellows
508	$f_{assembly}$	Reduction of the energy absorbed by the receiver due to assembly errors
509	FF	Fouling factor
510	h_{c1}	Specific enthalpy of the condensate in evaporator 1 at T_{c1} , J/kg
511	h_{Ci}'	Specific enthalpy of the condensate in preheater i at T_{Vi}' , J/kg
512	h_{Ci}''	Specific enthalpy of the distillate exiting the flash box i at T_{Ci}'' , J/kg
513	h_{preh2}	Specific enthalpy of the feedwater inlet in preheater 1, J/kg
514	h_{sc}	Specific enthalpy of condensed steam at T_s , J/kg
515	h_{V1}'	Specific enthalpy of the vapour at T_{V1}' , J/kg
516	h_{Vi}''	Specific enthalpy of the vapour at T_{Vi}'' , J/kg
517	K_{iam}	Incidence angle modifier, -
518	k_s	Salt permeability, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot s)$
519	k_w	Water permeability, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot s \cdot kPa)$
520	M_b	Brine flow rate from the RO unit, m^3/h
521	M_d	Permeate flow rate from the RO unit, m^3/h
522	M_f	Feedwater flow rate entering the RO unit, m^3/h
523	n_e	Number of elements
524	N_v	Number of pressure vessels
525	p	Steam pressure, Pa
526	q_{B1}	Mass flow rate of brine in effect 1, kg/s
527	q_{Ci}	Mass flow rate of condensate exiting flashing box i , kg/s
528	q_{D1}	Mass flow rate of vapor produced by boiling in effect 1, kg/s

529	q_{dsh}	Mass flow rate of water to desuperheater, kg/s
530	$q_{F,k}$	Mass flow rate of feedwater entering effect k , kg/s
531	q_{FBi}	Mass flow rate of vapor produced in flashing box i , kg/s
532	q_s	Mass flow rate of heating steam, kg/s
533	q_{suc}	Mass flow rate of entrained steam, kg/s
534	q_{Ti}	Total mass flow rate of vapor in effect i , kg/s
535	q_v	Mass flow rate of vapor, kg/s
536	\dot{Q}_1	Heat transfer rate in evaporator 1, W
537	T_{CF}	Temperature correction factor
538	T_i	Temperature in effect i , °C
539	T_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor in effect i , °C
540	T'_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor after demister in effect i , °C
541	T''_{V_i}	Temperature of the vapor in flash box i , °C
542	$T_{Vsat,i}$	Saturation temperature of the vapor in effect i , °C
543	$T_{c,i}$	Condensation temperature in effect i , °C
544	t_{prehi}	Feedwater temperature exiting preheater i , °C
545	$T_{s,sh}$	Temperature of superheated steam, °C
546	U_{e1}	Overall heat transfer coefficient of evaporator 1, W/(m ² °C)
547	X_{av}	Average salt concentration, ppm
548	X_b	Brine concentration, ppm
549	X_d	Permeate concentration, ppm
550	X_F	Salinity of feedwater, ppm
551		
552	Greek	
553	α	Absorbance of the receiver, -
554	α_s	Solar altitude, rad
555	α_1	Mass fraction of vapor condensed in preheater 1, -
556	β_{tilt}	Angle of the collector's axis to the local horizontal, rad
557	γ_s	Solar azimuth, rad
558	γ_{col}	Collector's orientation angle, rad
559	η_T	Isentropic efficiency of the steam turbine, -

560	η_{gen}	Efficiency of the electric generator, -
561	$\eta_{opt,0}$	Peak optical efficiency, -
562	η_P	Pump efficiency, -
563	θ	Incidence angle, rad
564	λ_s	Specific enthalpy of vaporization of water at T_s , J/kg
565	ρ	Reflectivity of the parabolic mirrors, -
566	ρ_f	Feed density, kg/m ³
567	τ	Transmissivity of the receiver glass cover, -
568	π	Osmotic pressure, kPa
569		
570	<i>Superscripts</i>	
571	'	Conditions of the vapor/condensate after the demister
572	"	Conditions of the vapor/condensate in the flashing boxes

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: